

AUSBILDUNG

Masterarbeiten der PH Zürich

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Anti-Bias Approaches to Visual Storytelling using Avatar: The Last Airbender

Abstract

This thesis developed an anti-bias media analysis framework to critically analyse visual storytelling and character representation in media, with the aim of developing approaches for implementing anti-bias education in the Swiss secondary EFL classroom. Based on anti-bias education (Derman-Sparks 1989; DermanSparks and Edwards 2010), the Learning for Justice's Social Justice Standards (Chiariello et al. 2022), critical literacy (McLaughlin and Devoogd 2004; Freitag-Hild 2022), Eder's (2010) Clock of Character, Doelker's (2015) visual literacy model, and Doering's (2013) affective-cognitive theory, the study merged these frameworks and theories into one coherent tool for analysing media through an anti-bias lens. Using this framework, the study conducts a qualitative, critical, multimodal analysis of four episodes from the series Avatar: The Last Airbender, focusing on the character Zuko.

The analysis reveals Zuko's shifting identity, his cross-cultural relationships, the audiovisual coding of trauma and power, and his moral transformation. The framework illuminates how audiovisual and narrative elements can challenge stereotypes, explore multiperspectivity, reveal systemic injustice, and highlight the risks and possibilities of moral action. Findings demonstrate that fictional media can provide a space for students to analyse complex social issues while still being able to connect them to real-world contexts. The developed framework proved useful for guiding interpretation and designing classroom activities that foster anti-bias competences and critical media literacy. Building on this, the thesis outlines guiding principles and task ideas for applying the framework to Avatar: The Last Airbender and for adapting it to other forms of media.

Keywords

Anti-Bias Education, Critical Media Literacy, Character Representation, Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework, Avatar: The Last Airbender

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Anti-Bias Approaches to Visual Storytelling using Avatar: The Last Airbender

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Secondary Education Level I

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Abstract

This thesis developed an anti-bias media analysis framework to critically analyse visual storytelling and character representation in media, with the aim of developing approaches for implementing anti-bias education in the Swiss secondary EFL classroom. Based on anti-bias education (Derman-Sparks 1989; Derman-Sparks and Edwards 2010), the Learning for Justice's Social Justice Standards (Chiariello et al. 2022), critical literacy (McLaughlin and DeVogd 2004; Freitag-Hild 2022), Eder's (2010) Clock of Character, Doelker's (2015) visual literacy model, and Doering's (2013) affective-cognitive theory, the study merged these frameworks and theories into one coherent tool for analysing media through an anti-bias lens. Using this framework, the study conducts a qualitative, critical, multimodal analysis of four episodes from the series *Avatar: The Last Airbender*, focusing on the character Zuko.

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Findings demonstrate that fictional media can provide a space for students to analyse complex social issues while still being able to connect them to real-world contexts. The developed framework proved useful for guiding interpretation and designing classroom activities that foster anti-bias competences and critical media literacy. Building on this, the thesis outlines guiding principles and task ideas for applying the framework to *Avatar: The Last Airbender* and for adapting it to other forms of media.

Key Words: Anti-Bias Education, Social Justice Standards, media literacy, visual literacy, critical literacy, multimodality, character analysis, affective-cognitive theory, secondary EFL, *Avatar: The Last Airbender (A:TLA)*

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1. Introduction

1.1 Topic and Context

Children's and young adolescents' media, which includes television series, films, books, and especially social media, play a significant role in shaping how young people perceive and understand themselves, others, and the complex societal structures around them (Derman-Sparks 2016). Far from being just apolitical or mere entertainment (Saurer 2019, 3), media made with intention reflect and reproduce important norms, ideologies, and social attitudes regarding identity, diversity, inequality, and power structures (Derman-Sparks 2016). Every piece of media is situated in specific social and historical contexts that both influence and are influenced by the world (Saurer 2019, 2).

In an increasingly complex sociopolitical landscape and during a time in which young people are continuously exposed to so much visual media and algorithmically filtered content, English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers face the challenge of developing language skills, critical thinking, media literacy, and the fostering of socio-cultural awareness through authentic and engaging material (Lightbown and Spada 2006, 113; Derman-Sparks 2016). Teachers must equip students with tools to decode media.

While most media studies often focus on literary realism to discuss real-world issues of representation and power (Saurer 2019, 3), this research focuses specifically on fictional and animated media, particularly those aimed at young audiences, as such texts carry equally meaningful messages. These messages are made accessible to young learners and provide powerful opportunities for critical and anti-bias-oriented media analysis.

This study is the intersection of two educational goals: fostering media literacy and promoting anti-bias education (ABE). Developed by Louise Derman-Sparks and the A.B.C. Task Force in 1989 with "Anti-Bias Curriculum – Tools for Empowering Young Children", anti-bias education is an approach that centres four core goals aimed at helping learners develop positive self-concepts, appreciate human diversity, recognise

unfairness, and engage in action to address bias (Derman-Sparks and Edwards 2010, 4-5).

Although Derman-Sparks' work lies primarily in early childhood pedagogy, ABE's goals do resonate with students in multilingual and multicultural contexts such as the Swiss secondary EFL classroom. Yet its application to the critical analysis of multimodal, fictional youth media narratives remains unexplored. This study addresses this gap by developing a structural analytical approach for the classroom that integrates anti-bias education, critical literacy, and media analysis. Research gaps are further discussed in detail in Sections 2.1 and 2.2.

1.2 Example *Avatar: The Last Airbender*

Avatar: The Last Airbender (A:TLA) (2005-2008), a globally popular and critically acclaimed series for over 20 years now, provides a rich example for analysis because of its storytelling, complex character development, and explicit engagement with themes of imperialism, cultural genocide, privilege, multiculturalism, and social justice (Kerr 2024, 1027-1028).

There has been some research done on *A:TLA* (see Section 2.2), but nothing that focuses on its potential as a classroom resource. Its distinctive multimodal storytelling drawing on cultural inspirations predominantly from South Asia and East Asia (Kerr 2024, 1027) and combining complex character design, symbolic imagery, plots, and audiovisual elements, provides a medium through which students can learn to analyse how meaning is constructed through visuals and narratives critically. The show's analysis is crucial for understanding how complex issues are communicated to younger audiences. The active fan engagement with the series over the past twenty years (Van Hoey 2022, 203) and relevance across generations further underlines its cultural relevance and its potential as a meaningful text for exploring anti-bias themes in multilingual and multicultural learning environments.

Zuko's character arc is particularly suited for a focused anti-bias media analysis. His narrative, which deals with identity conflict, privilege, and transformation, illustrates how fictional characters represent meaning and how young viewers engage emotionally and cognitively with them.

1.3 Aim and Research Questions

The primary aim of this thesis is to develop a practical framework for critically analysing young adolescents' media through an anti-bias lens, with emphasis on its applicability in the secondary EFL classroom. This educational approach aims to contribute to more inclusive learning environments.

To achieve this, the thesis synthesises frameworks and concepts from anti-bias education (Derman-Sparks 1989; Derman-Sparks and Edwards 2010; Chiarello et al. 2022), critical literacy (McLaughlin and DeVogd 2004), visual literacy (Doelker 2015), affective-cognitive theory (Doering 2013), and character analysis (Eder 2010) into a coherent framework for anti-bias media interpretation. Using Zuko's arc in *Avatar: The Last Airbender*, the study investigates how this framework can reveal constructions of identity, injustice, power, and agency within a television series. Lastly, these insights are used to develop classroom activities for *A:TLA* and their broader application to different media beyond just the show.

This study is guided by the following research questions:

- RQ1.** How can existing anti-bias frameworks be adapted for use in critically analysing visual storytelling and character representation in media to address social issues?
- RQ2.** How can character representation in *Avatar: The Last Airbender* serve as an example for applying anti-bias media analysis frameworks to promote inclusive and critical learning in the secondary EFL classroom?
- RQ3.** How can the adapted framework be transferred and applied across diverse media to support anti-bias education and critical media literacy?

1.4 Personal Research Interest

Even before I knew of anti-bias education, its principles resonated with what I wanted for my teaching. When I formally encountered the framework, it immediately aligned with the goals I already had. Although I realised quickly that applying these principles in practice can be challenging, having a structured framework with guiding questions and adaptable strategies for analysing different forms of visual narrative media is very valuable for my future teaching. I have always wanted to use more books and television shows in my classes but often lacked a clear analytical approach. Viewing them through the lens of anti-bias education and using *A:TLA* as an example finally brought these interests together.

My connection to *A:TLA* is personal. I first watched it at four years old when it originally aired and was drawn to its creativity, characters, and stories. Revisiting it over the years, I was always struck by how well it holds up, both narratively and thematically. Now, two decades later, the show has made a lasting impression not only on me but also on many others around me.

The show conveys important messages without talking down to its young audience, and it resists offering overly simplistic or “perfect” solutions to complex problems. Its nuanced engagement with social issues makes it an ideal text for exploring the possibilities of anti-bias education in the secondary EFL classroom.

1.5 Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is structured into eight chapters.

Chapter 2 provides the theoretical and conceptual foundations for the study. It outlines anti-bias education, situates the research within existing research on anti-bias education and *Avatar: The Last Airbender*, and introduces key definitions, concepts, and relevant frameworks related to anti-bias education, critical literacy, and visual analysis.

Chapter 3 presents the methodological approach. It explains the qualitative critical multimodal analysis approach for this thesis, introduces the analytical corpus, and explains

the synthesis of the selected theories and models into a single anti-bias media analysis framework.

Chapter 4 applies this model to a critical analysis of Zuko's character arc across four key episodes, demonstrating how identity, justice, and action are constructed through narrative and audiovisual elements.

Chapter 5 interprets these findings and discusses their pedagogical relevance for the secondary EFL classroom.

Chapter 6 translates these interpretations into practical classroom strategies, including ideas for classroom activities and guiding principles for implementing the framework beyond *A:TLA*.

Chapter 7 addresses methodological and conceptual limitations and outlines directions for future research.

Chapter 8 concludes by answering the research questions and summarising the study's contributions.

2. Theoretical and Conceptual Foundations

The goal of this chapter is to provide the theoretical and conceptual basis for analysing *Avatar: The Last Airbender* through an anti-bias lens and for developing a pedagogical framework suitable for the secondary English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom in Switzerland. The chapter begins with an overview of anti-bias education. It then situates this thesis within previous research on *Avatar: The Last Airbender*. Third, it discusses and defines key conceptual foundations and terms important for the analysis of *A:TLA*. Finally, it reviews existing frameworks relevant to anti-bias education, critical literacy, and media analysis. The chapter concludes by summarising the validity and limitations of the selected frameworks and by synthesising their relevance for the study.

2.1 Anti-Bias Education: Research and Practice

Anti-bias education is grounded in Paulo Freire's "Pedagogy of the Oppressed" (1970), where he defines education as "the practice of freedom," which is "the means by which men and women deal creatively with reality and discover how to participate in the transformation of their world" ([1970] 2005, 34). Anti-bias education emerged in the United States in the late twentieth century (Escayg 2019, 3) with Derman-Sparks (1998) as she established its foundational principles. Later, they were expanded by Derman-Sparks and Edwards (2010, 4-5) into four central goals: developing positive social identities, recognising diversity, understanding and challenging unfairness, and taking action for justice.

These goals were further operationalised by Learning for Justice's widely used Social Justice Standards (SJS), organised into the domains of Identity, Diversity, Justice, and Action (IDJA) (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3). The SJS provides concrete, teachable competences, aims, and prompts that are highly applicable to EFL settings.

Derman-Sparks' work in ABE largely concentrates on early-childhood and elementary settings, where identity formation and social-emotional learning are in their beginning stages, and children are more open to exploring new ideas and ways of life (Derman-Sparks and Edwards 2010, 8). Derman-Sparks and Edwards (2010, 2, 8) emphasise teacher self-reflection, classroom climate, and sustained engagement with bias rather

than one-off activities. However, these concepts have also been expanded to K-12 levels and teacher education contexts, just not as deeply (Woo et al. 2022; Lin et al. 2008). A substantial body of research done in the U.S. by RAND demonstrates that explicitly teaching about the four domains of anti-bias education can lead to “positive academic, attitudinal, and behavioural outcomes” (Woo et al. 2022, 1).

Specific research on ABE in Switzerland is scarce, though similar concepts, such as upholding humanitarian democratic values, developing social and intercultural competences, and promoting inclusivity, which reflect the core aims of ABE, are present in the cantonal curriculum of Zurich (Lehrplan 21 2017). The alignment between ABE and the Lehrplan 21 indicates its potential for Swiss secondary EFL teaching, where students can engage with authentic media and negotiate meaning through language.

ABE shares aims with other equity-oriented educational frameworks. Ladson-Billings (1995, 160) culturally relevant pedagogy emphasises academic success, cultural competence, and the development of critical consciousness. Geneva Gay’s (2002, 106) culturally responsive teaching centres the integration of students’ cultural backgrounds into curriculum and instruction. While ABE aligns with these approaches through its focus on representation and social awareness, it extends their reach by addressing a broader spectrum of social identities and emphasising structural injustice and collective action.

Research in the U.S has shown that English-Language-Arts (ELA) and general elementary teachers are more likely to incorporate anti-bias themes, as literary texts, discussion-based instructions, and reflective writing naturally lend themselves to exploring social identity and justice (Woo et al. 2022, 6). Teachers who participated in the study found that curriculum materials often do not adequately address ABE topics, leading them to use alternative or self-designed materials (Woo et al. 2022, 2). When teachers design their own material, they often draw from contemporary media and frequently integrate this work with social and emotional learning (SEL) curricula rather than with explicitly anti-bias resources such as Learning for Justice or Facing History (Woo et al. 2022, 10).

Across K-12 levels, researchers have identified an uneven emphasis across the four domains of ABE. Most materials tend to address Identity and Diversity more deeply than Justice and Action (Woo et al. 2022, 11). This imbalance indicates a gap and a need for models that help teachers and students to move beyond recognition towards engagement and moral action. This study tries to respond to this gap by also focusing on themes of structural injustice and moral agency through media analysis and providing materials to use in the classroom.

2.2 Avatar: The Last Airbender and Existing Research

Avatar: The Last Airbender is a children's animated television show created by Bryan Konietzko and Michael Dante DiMartino, which aired on Nickelodeon from 2005 to 2008. In *A:TLA*, the world is divided into four nations: the Fire Nation, the Water Tribes, the Air Nomads, and the Earth Kingdom. "Benders" can manipulate the elements from their respective nations using martial arts and magic (Perlmutter 2018, 50-51). The Avatar, however, can master all four elements and is meant to maintain peace in the world, especially when the Fire Nation began an imperial war. Meanwhile, the Fire Nation prince, Zuko, has been banished from his home and was sent to capture the Avatar so that he can restore his honour. A detailed synopsis of Zuko's arc is provided in Appendix E.

Existing research on the series is sparse and scattered across different themes. Most scholarly contributions focus on isolated themes from the show, like feminism, genocide, colonialism, or individual characters, often in the form of thesis projects or standalone journal articles.

Aslam and Adqas (2024) offer a linguistic and critical analysis of the series, exploring how *A:TLA* represents cultural genocide and power relations through dialogue and narrative structures. Their work positions *A:TLA* as an example of how children's media can communicate serious socio-political realities, but their focus remains primarily on linguistic textual analysis rather than educational application.

Kerr (2024) examines the series through Michael Billig's concept of banal nationalism. They argue that even while *A:TLA* critiques imperialism, it nonetheless reproduces

nationalist worldviews by presenting the division of the world into nations as natural. Kerr (2024, 1024) also emphasises that rather than looking at the villains of the show, it is much more important to look at the structures that help them have this power. This work is useful for identifying how subtle ideological messages can be incorporated into children's media and offers a critical reading of the imperialism and nationalism portrayed in the show.

Saurer (2019) investigates *A:TLA* in relation to cultural identity, hybridity, and pluralism, applying postcolonial theories by Homi Bhabha and Stuart Hall to show how the series handles belonging, living in diaspora, and intercultural encounters. Her emphasis on hybridity and plural societies offers a view on how *A:TLA* represents inclusive perspectives and complex cultural interactions.

Van Hoey (2022) uses conceptual blending theory by Fauconnier and Turner (2003) to explore how audiences engage with *A:TLA* through internet memes and pop culture. His work shows how viewers interact with the series year after airing and how they use the show's symbolism to comment on real-world issues. This insight was important for understanding how media can facilitate critical reflection beyond what is explicitly depicted.

Discussions around the series online also highlight its cultural and aesthetic blend. The series draws from diverse cultural traditions like Japanese, Chinese, Tibetan, Buddhist, and Hindu cultures, while framing them through an U.S.-American narrative and creative lens (Van Hoey 2022, 189). This creates a blended space by combining multiple cultural codes within one fictional universe (Fauconnier and Turner 2003, 58-59; Van Hoey 2022, 189). It also has a unique hybrid aesthetic as it visually combines Japanese anime-inspired techniques with U.S. cinematic traditions (Vasconcellos 2007).

Despite research showing that *A:TLA* can be a significant site for discussions about identity, ideology, and culture, the academic landscape is bare, as most analyses are either theoretical, linguistic, or cultural. There is a research gap regarding how *A:TLA* can be systematically explored through an anti-bias lens, and how the series could be integrated into the secondary EFL classroom. Drawing on the conceptual contributions of Kerr, Saurer, and Van Hoey, this project aims to bring together pedagogical

frameworks, critical literacy, and media literacy to demonstrate how *A:TLA*'s multi-modal construction of identity, injustice, and transformation, particularly through Zuko's character arc, can support ABE within EFL contexts.

2.3 Conceptual Foundations and Key Definitions

To analyse visual and narrative construction through an anti-bias lens, several conceptual foundations are central, like representation and bias, identity formation, ideology and power, and creating meaning through multimodality. These concepts and important terms will be discussed and defined in the following sections.

2.3.1 Representation and Bias

Representation is, as Stuart Hall (1997, 16) defines, "the production of meaning through language". It is a practice by which members of a culture use signs and symbols (words, images, sounds, etc.) to stand for or represent concepts, ideas, and feelings to other people (Hall 1997, 1). His constructionist view of representation emphasises that while things exist in the world, they only take on meaning through social and cultural construction, which can vary across cultures (Hall 1997, 22, 25). In the EFL ABE classroom, this allows for examining how meanings are culturally shaped and negotiated collectively and making space for different interpretations.

Identity is defined by Hall (1996, 4) as a process of "becoming" rather than something fixed. He emphasises that identity evolves through negotiation and is constructed within different historical and institutional contexts. Identity is more so marked by difference and exclusion than by unity. In *A:TLA*, Saurer (2019, 41) explained how characters experience identity in the form of two main narratives. For some characters, displacement deepens the understanding of their cultural origins and fosters growth through contact with other people in a pluralistic world. For others, the loss of home and confrontation with unfamiliar surroundings break former identities and force them to rethink their worldview.

Bias plays an important role in representation as it affects how things are perceived. Bias is defined by Derman-Sparks (1989, 3) as "any attitudes, belief, or feeling that

results in, and helps to justify unfair treatment of an individual because of his or her identity.” On the flip side, anti-bias is established as:

An active/activist approach to challenging prejudice, stereotyping, bias, and the ‘isms’. In a society in which institutional structures create and maintain sexism, racism, and handicappism, it is not sufficient to be non-biased (and also highly unlikely), nor is it sufficient to be an observer. It is necessary for each individual to actively intervene, to challenge and counter the personal and institutional behaviours that perpetuate oppression. (Derman-Sparks 1989, 3)

ABE is therefore not understood as a passive awareness model but as an active pedagogy that requires learners and educators to challenge prejudice and discriminatory systems.

Media always contain biases, some are subtle, others are more overt, ranging from stereotypes and tokenism to the bigger problem of invisibility of certain groups, which can undermine a child’s self-concept or reinforce prejudiced ideas (Derman-Sparks 2016). “Stereotype” can be defined as “a preconceived and oversimplified idea of the characteristics which typify a person (...)” (OED, 2025). Derman-Sparks (1989, 3) also points out that stereotypes “usually carry derogatory implications”. Stereotypes function as cognitive schemas that individuals use to process social information efficiently, but at the cost of accuracy, fairness, and recognition of individuality (Hilton and Hippel 1996, 240-41). Within the Social Justice Standards, students are encouraged to view individuals as unique rather than representatives of groups (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3).

Tokenism is defined by Rosabeth M. Kanter (1977, as cited by Dalkiliç and Yilmaz 2019, 205-7) as the “artificial inclusion” of small number of individuals from a minority group into a dominant group, based on characteristic such as gender, race, religion, or age, to give the appearance of equality or diversity without granting real power or influence.

Another form of tokenism is performative actions, which are often referred to in the context of social movements as performative activism. They are broadly understood as inauthentic displays of support motivated by personal benefit rather than by genuine concern for the disadvantaged group, and they often fall short of creating genuine social change (Kutlaca and Radke 2022, 2). By contrast, intentional inclusion entails

systemic change where all individuals feel valued, respected, and empowered (Luder 2017, 9; 12).

In the classroom, the distinction between tokenism, performative actions, and intentional inclusion is critical. Understanding the differences helps teachers and students make choices that genuinely show support rather than merely signalling support. Teachers promote diversity and identity development by providing mirrors, materials that reflect students' own experiences, and windows, resources that reveal lives and perspectives different from their own (Bishop 2015). This aligns with the goals of anti-bias education to affirm identity, foster empathy, and help prevent injustice by ensuring that a wide range of realities are acknowledged and discussed (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3).

Another goal of anti-bias education is to ensure students have the skills to act against “discriminatory actions” (Derman-Sparks 2010, 5). This aligns with the concept of moral agency, which refers to “the knowledge of social norms and morally right behaviour as well as the ability to evaluate and adapt one’s own actions against these standards, and therefore to know about the ‘morally correct actions’ in a given situation” (Sondermann et al. 2018, 3). Research has identified that moral agency is influenced by the socio-political contexts in which a child grows up (Montreuil et al. 2018, 21-22). While children certainly require protection due to their developmental needs, they also possess moral reasoning and the ability to engage in ethical reflection (Montreuil et al. 2018, 18). Recognising this duality is needed to respect children’s voices and experiences. Fostering moral agency within ABE involves providing opportunities for children to recognise moral agency in media and to be moral agents themselves. These skills are directly tied to SJS’ Justice and Action goals (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3).

2.3.2 Ideology, Imperialism, and the In-Between

To understand how the Fire Nation functions and the influence it has on other nations and Zuko, central concepts rooted in real-world politics, such as ideologies, imperialism, authoritarianism, and nationalism, are important to examine.

An ideology is a structured set of beliefs that interprets how society and the world function, while also justifying systems of power and aiming to influence or transform them. They often seek and attract followers and are often at the forefront of any kind of social movement (Cranston 2025).

Imperialism can be defined as a “state policy, practice, or advocacy of extending power and dominion especially by direct territorial acquisition or by gaining political and economic control of other areas.” (Britannica Editors 2025). While the terms imperialism and colonialism are often used interchangeably, the Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy explains that the former refers to broader forms of political, economic, or military domination by one state over another, whereas the latter specifically entails establishing colonies and direct rule (Kohn and Reddy 2023). Although the Fire Nation’s expansion also reflects elements of colonialism and imperialism, for this thesis, the term imperialism is used as an umbrella concept to describe all of the Fire Nation’s actions in *A:TLA*.

Authoritarianism describes a political system in which power is concentrated in the hands of a single leader or a small elite, where citizens do not enjoy full civil liberties or political rights, opposition is restricted, and any objections are met with punishment (Lindstaedt 2025). Authoritarian regimes are marked by propaganda, cult of personality, and nationalism. Propaganda uses media, education, and art to influence public perception and to promote the regime’s ideology, legitimise its rules, and erase alternative perspectives (Smith 2025). In a cult of personality, the leader is glorified as a heroic or divine figure, creating loyalty and discouraging criticism (Kulik 2025).

Audi (2009, 366, 371) defines nationalism as loyalty, superiority, preference for, and moral obligation towards one’s nation, often at the expense of the interests and welfare of humanity as a whole. At the extreme end, national interest overrides everything, encapsulating the phrase “my country right or wrong” (Audi 2009, 367).

The concept of the in-between helps explain how new cultural meanings and identities emerge when rigid divisions and systems, such as colonizer and colonized, are broken down. Bhabha ([1994] 2012, 2) defines the in-between as the zone where domains of difference overlap and where new identities are formed. These spaces question simple

binary divisions and create new “strategies of selfhood – singular or communal – that initiate new signs of identity, and innovative sites of collaboration, and contestation, in the act of defining the idea of society itself” ([1994] 2012, 2).

2.3.3 Multimodality and Narrative Construction

A TV show is multimodal in nature. Multimodality is defined by Kress and Van Leeuwen (2001, 20) as the study of communication that draws on different resources or “modes” at the same time. Its central aim is to understand how meaning is created and negotiated when these modes come together for a product (Kress and Van Leeuwen 2001, 111). These modes include diverse semiotic modes like “language, image, music, sound, texture, and gesture” (Kress and Van Leeuwen 2001, Preface), and rather than focusing on one single form of mode, it examines how these modes function both together and independently across semiotic layers (Kress and Van Leeuwen 2001, 2).

Character analysis is central to this thesis because it allows for a systematic evaluation of how fictional figures reflect and influence society. Eder (2010, 18) describes a character as a “fictional being with an inner life that exists as a communicatively constructed artifact”. Characters are a form of representation. The defining feature that differentiates characters from passive elements of a story world is that they are carriers of meaning, perception, emotions, and ideology (Eder 2010, 17). How to systematically analyse a character will be elaborated more in Section 2.4.3.

Where individual character analysis focuses on singular figures, character constellations examine the total systems of all relationships among the characters within a fictional world (Eder 2010, 29-30). Character constellations operate on two levels: characters as fictional beings within a social world and as artifacts fulfilling dramaturgical functions. These layers interact dynamically. Roles such as protagonist, antagonist, or helpers embody cultural and moral values and social hierarchies. Characters are perceived through comparison with others, which emphasises their unique features and their development (Eder 2010, 31).

Conceptual blending theory explains the cognitive mechanisms behind the complex world-building in *A:TLA* and how viewers can project fictional worlds onto the real world.

A blended space is explained by Fauconnier and Turner (2003, 58-59) as a mental construction that forms when two different ideas or concepts are combined in a mind to create something new with its own meaning. The brain merges two separate “input spaces” into a blend that compresses complex information into an unified picture. The resulting structure can emerge from combining elements to form new relationships or from unconsciously drawing on familiar backgrounds (Fauconnier and Turner 2003, 60). Blending theory is crucial for media analysis because the compressed concepts that drive the narrative often mask complicated or hidden assumptions (Fauconnier and Turner 2003, 63).

A:TLA applies this process to its world-building and character design. The four nations are blends of real-world cultures and philosophies, such as Tibetan Buddhism (Air Nomads), Inuit traditions (Water Tribe), and Chinese martial arts (Earth Kingdom). The narrative also blends generic hero storylines structures (good vs. evil) with elements from real-world socio-political issues (imperialism, genocide). On a character level, blending appears through identities that contain multitudes, discouraging putting characters into boxes (Van Hoey 2022, 188-189).

2.4 Existing Frameworks in Anti-Bias Education, Critical Literacy, and Media Analysis

The theoretical foundations above intersect with several educational and multimodal analytical frameworks below, which will guide the anti-bias media analysis framework developed in Chapter 3.

To answer research question 1 and to develop a framework for analysing a series through an anti-bias education lens, the Social Justice Standards framework provides the overarching structure, which is then further supported by McLaughlin and Devoogd’s (2004) concepts of Critical Literacy, alongside Freitag-Hild’s (2022) discussion of this concept, Eder’s (2010) *The Clock of Character* for character analysis in film, and Doelker’s (2015) principals for Visual Literacy combined with Doering’s (2013) affective cognitive theory. These theories offer both theoretical grounding and analytical tools for character representation and interpretation.

2.4.1 Social Justice Standards (SJS) – Learning for Justice (2022)

The Social Justice Standards (SJS) by Learning for Justice are divided into four domains: Identity, Diversity, Justice, and Action (IDJA). Each domain contains specific goals that provide an anchor for standards and learning outcomes. They are designed to foster a deep understanding of one's own identity and that of others, developing skills related to reducing prejudice and fostering collective action (Chiariello et al. 2022, 2). These domains allow teachers to scaffold classroom discussions and tasks, making it especially useful for EFL settings.

The Identity domain focuses on students “developing positive social identities based on their membership in multiple groups in society” (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3). It involves exploring personal background, family structures, cultural context, and negotiating one's identity with the dominant culture. The Diversity domain helps students to become comfortable and respectful when interacting with people of different backgrounds. It emphasises the development of respectful language in an open-minded dialogue to foster empathy and connection across differences. The Justice domain explores fairness, equity, and systemic inequality. It encourages critical thinking about bias, discrimination, privilege, and the systems that support or challenge injustice. Finally, the Action domain encourages individuals to turn knowledge, empathy, and reflection into real-world action. It wants to move beyond understanding injustice towards developing the courage, responsibility, and skills to challenge it (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3).

2.4.2 McLaughlin and DeVoogd's Critical Literacy Approach (2004)

Based on McLaughlin and DeVoogd's (2004) approach to critical literacy, Freitag-Hild (2022, 110) promotes critical literacy as the competence to reflect critically and question beliefs, texts, representations, and power dynamics in literature with the goal of promoting sustainable social and political change. Here, the concept of “reading the word” is linked to interpreting and acting upon the world, or “reading the world” (Freire and Macedo 1987, as quoted in Freitag-Hild 2022, 109-110). It pushes the reader, or the viewer, to ask: “Whose voices are centred or excluded? What power relations are represented in the narrative?” (McLaughlin and DeVoogd 2004, 56).

McLaughlin and DeVogd (2004, 54-55) state that critical literacy in literature is defined by questioning and challenging ideals, power, transformation, and action, by focusing on the problem and its complexity, and by seeking out multiple perspectives. These points have been further supported with ideas for classroom activities. Freitag-Hild (2022, 113-114) then, based on the objectives by McLaughlin and DeVogd, clearly defined four dimensions to support critical literacy, which are 1) creating irritation, 2) making multiperspectivity tangible, 3) reflecting on sociopolitical issues, and 4) fostering participation and social engagement. This model encourages learners to interrogate character development, the particular choice of words, narrative perspectives, and the social norms embedded in fiction (Freitag-Hild 2022, 112).

The creating irritation dimension aims to question and challenge established ways of thinking and seeing the world (McLaughlin and DeVogd 2004, 54; Freitag-Hild 2022, 113). Multiperspectivity encourages exploring a story through different points of view, especially those of people who are marginalised, not fully represented, or represented only in harmful, stereotypical ways. It helps the viewer to break away from the dominant viewpoint and understand how identities like class, gender, race, and age shape experiences (McLaughlin and DeVogd 2004, 55; Freitag-Hild 2022, 113). Sociopolitical reflection uncovers the power structures within a story. It asks the watcher to analyse how power, privilege, and social roles affect characters' interactions and life outcomes and how these dynamics reflect real-world issues such as patriarchy, racism, and imperialism (McLaughlin and DeVogd 2004, 56; as cited in Freitag-Hild 2022, 113-14). The fostering participation and social engagement dimension emphasises that the process of critical literacy is beyond just contemplating issues but moving towards real-world change. This happens by reflection, transformation, action, and taking responsibility for problems in texts as well as in the real world (McLaughlin and DeVogd 2004, 54; Freitag-Hild 2022, 114).

Films and TV shows serve as valuable multimodal texts for engaging with these dimensions of critical literacy. Through guided viewing and discussion, students can question how particular scenes reinforce or challenge dominant ideologies and social norms. Film offers a dynamic way to connect textual critique with audiovisual interpretation.

2.4.3 Eder's Clock of Character (2010)

Eder's (2010) Clock of Character is a framework for character analysis in visual media, such as animated series, that considers viewer perception and cultural context. It breaks down characters into four dimensions: Artifacts, Fictional Beings, Symbols, and Symptoms. Eder's framework fosters deeper engagement with how identity and social symbolism are interpreted by audiences (Eder 2010, 16).

The Artifact dimension deals with how a character is presented and shaped through audiovisual elements such as camera angles, lighting, costume, voice, music, and performance. It focuses on the formal and stylistic choices that shape the character. The Fictional Being dimension is about who the character is in the fictional world by examining their thoughts, emotions, body language, relationships, and goals. The Symbol dimension analyses the deeper meaning the character represents, such as values, ideologies, or social themes like justice, rebellion, or redemption. The last dimension, Symptom, is about how a character reflects society and culture, including the creators' intentions and audience reception within a specific sociocultural context (Eder 2010, 21-22).

From an anti-bias perspective, examining a character as a fictional being, symbol, and symptom allows the viewers to see why they were created in a particular way, what messages they carry, and how their portrayal conveys those messages.

2.4.4 Doelker's Visual Literacy Model (2015)

Media Literacy means being able to use media consciously and responsibly. It includes understanding how media can meet individual needs for information and entertainment, while also questioning media content and personal consumption (Suess et al. 2018, 116). And much like reading a written text, visual literacy specifically refers to the ability to critically understand, interpret, and make meaning from signs and images within a cultural and communicative system (Doelker 2015, 21).

Doelker's (2015) model for visual literacy provides a framework for analysing how meaning is constructed through visual media. Through eight semantic layers levels of

image interpretation are described: “1) spontaneous meaning (nonverbal signals), 2) fixed meaning (conventionalised symbols), 3) latent meaning (symbolic meaning), 4) declared meaning (what the caption says), 5) articulated meaning (what the composition says) 6) contextual meaning (what the works as a whole says), 7) intertextual meaning (what the history of the motif says), and 8) transtextual meaning (what biography and contemporary history say)” (Doelker 2015, 42).

Complementing the semantic layers, Doelker outlines a three-step method for image reading. Here, the steps go from personal interpretation to critical analysis to understanding the creator’s intent. Adapted for the classroom, this approach supports students in moving from subjective impressions to a more grounded and reflective visual analysis.

The first step, the viewer speaks (subjective reaction), focuses on the viewer’s personal response to the image. Which associations, memories, or personal experiences does it trigger? This stage highlights that perception is inherently influenced by individual reception (Doelker 2015, 46). It validates the viewer’s initial impressions as meaningful and encourages personal engagement with media.

The second step, the image speaks (its inherent features and design), involves analysing the image’s formal and semantic layers. What meanings are embedded in its composition, colours, and perspective? The goal is to uncover the semantic potential of the image and what it could possibly communicate based on its design (Doelker 2015, 46). Viewers learn to identify visual elements with fixed, culturally shared meanings.

The last step, the author speaks (intended meaning), shifts attention to the intention behind creating the image. This may include titles, captions, interviews, the creator’s wider body of work, and broader socio-historical context. This step is more research-oriented, thus encouraging students to look beyond the image and situate it in larger cultural and historical contexts (Doelker 2015, 46).

2.4.5 Doering's affective-cognitive theory (2013)

Doering's (2013) affective-cognitive theory adds another layer to media literacy by examining how viewers relate to media figures through processes like empathy, social comparison, parasocial relationships, and identification. These processes explain how students emotionally and cognitively engage with, perceive, and internalise characters (Doering 2013, 296), but they are not themselves classroom learning theories or frameworks.

Empathy refers to the viewer's ability to cognitively and affectively feel with a media figure. It involves both perspective-taking, understanding why and how someone might feel (Davis 1996, as cited in Doering 2013, 197). Generally, cognitive empathy is needed to understand fictional character representation and to heighten entertainment and suspense, which then leads to stronger engagement with media messages. Higher emotional involvement in media can either encourage behavioural change or be manipulated and misused for emotionally charged propaganda and advertisements (Doering 2013, 299).

Social comparisons involve viewers comparing themselves against media figures either upwards, to someone superior, downwards to someone worse off, or horizontally, to someone similar (Doering 2013, 300). Upward comparison might encourage viewers to emulate their positive traits, but it might also damage self-esteem when the represented character is idealised and seems unattainable (Doering 2013, 301-302).

Parasocial relationships describe the illusion of a one-sided relationship with a media figure built over time (Doering 2013, 302). Viewers feel emotionally connected to a favourite character or a celebrity, experiencing genuine grief or joy in response to their lives. While such bonds can help with loneliness and identity exploration, the lack of reciprocity and a parasocial breakup can cause emotional distress (Doering 2013, 303).

Identification refers to a temporary merging of self and character, in which the viewer takes on the positive traits of a media figure. This can make the viewer feel like a hero, but it can also reinforce problematic ideals if those figures embody stereotypes or unrealistic values (Doering 2013, 305).

These four processes can make learning more immersive, personally meaningful, and encourage critical engagement as students develop a deeper understanding of why certain things are depicted the way they are. However, not all media effects can be consciously steered (Doering 2013, 308). Emotional responses differ for each person, shaped by social conditioning and neurological dispositions (Doering 2013, 297). This calls for a nuanced approach that balances the potential of critical media literacy and empathy training with awareness of media's limitations and risks.

2.5 Synthesis, Effectiveness, and Limitations of the Frameworks

The frameworks and theories outlined above offer different entry points into media analysis in a classroom setting focused on anti-bias education. The IDJA domains provide the overarching categories. Analysis can explore how characters and their portrayals address or relate to issues within these domains.

Critical Literacy encourages analysis of language, narrative patterns, and power relations. The Clock of Character adds a multi-perspective lens to character interpretation. Visual literacy enables the decoding of meaning in representations through design choices (colour, framing, costume, symbolism). And at last, the affective-cognitive theory describes how watchers might feel about character representation in media and how they process those feelings.

While each of the selected frameworks offers useful entry points for analysing media, there is little to no empirical research that tests their effectiveness generally, nor in the secondary classroom. However, the Learning for Justice Social Justice Standards are more widely used and operationalised, which has already been discussed in detail in Section 2.2. The other frameworks are mainly theoretical and have been used to guide analysis and reflection rather than as tested teaching models. Some of their ideas appear in broader research in media education, but there are no studies that clearly show measurable results based on these frameworks alone. Nevertheless, by synthesising these frameworks, it becomes possible to apply them meaningfully in a secondary school setting, allowing for a broader and more inclusive approach that would not be achievable by using them separately.

2.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter has outlined the theoretical and conceptual foundations and key definitions for this study. It introduced anti-bias education, highlighted the current research landscape on *Avatar: The Last Airbender*, and presented key concepts such as bias, identity, imperialism, and multimodality. It then reviewed frameworks from anti-bias education, critical literacy, character analysis, visual literacy, affective-cognitive theory, and discussed their potential and limitations for classroom use.

The following methodology chapter will describe how these frameworks complement one another and how they can be synthesised into a single analytical framework. This integrated model will then be applied to the analysis of *A:TLA* and to the design of classroom activities for secondary EFL learners.

3. Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodological approach guiding the study. It explains the qualitative and critical multimodal design, introduces the analytical corpus, presents the synthesised anti-bias media analysis framework, and describes the process through which the corpus was examined. It also acknowledges the researcher's positionality and addresses methodological limitations. The goal is to demonstrate how the theoretical foundations became an operational analytical tool that can be transferred into a practical classroom model.

3.1 Methodological approach

This study employs a qualitative critical multimodal analysis of selected episodes from *Avatar: The Last Airbender*. The analysis combines deductive reasoning, guided by the synthesised anti-bias media analysis framework, with inductive reasoning that focuses on patterns within scenes and on narrative development (Braun and Clarke 2024, 394). These forms of reasoning operate within an iterative process (Smith and McGannon 2024, 539). This dual approach supports the broader aim of developing a practical classroom model for the secondary EFL context because it provides both a structured framework for analysis and the flexibility for individual interpretations.

Qualitative research seeks to understand contextualised meanings and interpretations “that make the world visible” rather than numerical generalizations (Denzin et al. 2024, 14). A critical perspective questions and challenges societal standards and power structures to produce understanding and knowledge that confronts injustice (Kincheloe and McLaren 2011, 299-300).

Initially, prompts from the synthesised anti-bias framework guided the viewing of the four core episodes. During the analysis, inductive insights captured visual or narrative patterns that the framework did not anticipate. These observations were incorporated into refining the framework and ensuring that the theoretical grounding and research questions aligned with the findings (Braun and Clarke 2024, 393-395). This iterative process allows balancing structure and theory with openness to viewers' interpretations as the research progresses (Smith and McGannon 2024, 539).

This approach aligns closely with the research questions, which focus on how representations are depicted, decoded, and taught. Such inquiries call for an interpretative analysis instead of quantitative methods. It is also fitting for an animated series that communicates meaning through audiovisual design and narrative development. Finally, this approach supports classroom transfer, as the analytical tool and its insights can be translated into concrete prompts that help students to analyse media across genres critically.

3.2 Corpus

The corpus focuses on four Zuko-centred episodes across the whole series:

- Season 1, Episode 12: “The Storm”
- Season 2, Episode 7: “Zuko Alone”
- Season 2, Episode 20: “The Crossroads of Destiny”
- Season 3, Episode 12: “The Western Air Temple”

These episodes were selected because they offer a lot of information on Zuko and important story beats from his arc, as he is usually only featured in the B-plot. Zuko’s role in these episodes provides rich opportunities for discussion, as he is both extremely controversial and deeply beloved by fans for a reason. Emotionally charged media helps viewers to empathise with characters and engage more deeply with the narrative (Doering 2013, 296).

Zuko’s character arc offers a contained yet complex journey that reflects major anti-bias themes. “The Storm” deals with Zuko’s origins, shame, and displacement, setting the stage for questions of identity and belonging. “Zuko Alone” shifts focus to the effects of imperialism, class, and everyday subtleties of nationalism, revealing how his personal struggles intersect with bigger social structures. In “The Crossroads of Destiny” Zuko reaches a critical point in decision-making, having to choose between complicity and resistance. Finally, “The Western Air Temple” tackles themes of allyship and accountability, as Zuko reconciles with the Avatar.

The four episodes span the whole series, allowing the analysis to trace shifts in visual representation and the narrative over time. They also provide a manageable corpus for a deep, multimodal analysis that aligns with the scale of a qualitative project and with the classroom. Structuring classroom activities around these episodes can help students experience anti-bias learning in a narrative progression.

Using a fantasy animated series allows the exploration of complex issues without singling out real students or problems and lowering the barriers for a discussion about sensitive topics. Students can still talk about complicated issues without having the knowledge of real-world histories and politics. It enables students to connect fictional systems with real-world institutions with the help of the teacher, fostering transferable media literacy skills.

3.3 Analytical Tool: Synthesised Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework

This section explores how the individual components of the selected theories and frameworks align with and support one another and then synthesises them into a coherent analytical model for anti-bias media analysis. This model is composed of prompts for examining character representation and visual storytelling. It directly addresses RQ1 by demonstrating how different frameworks guide media analysis through an anti-bias lens.

3.3.1 Learning For Justice’s Social Justice Standards (2022) and McLaughlin and DeVoogd’s Critical Literacy (2004) as discussed by Freitag Hild (2022)

The SJS offers the overarching categories IDJA, but to apply these aims meaningfully, Critical Literacy supports them with analytical tasks:

- The Identity domain (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3) is deepened by “multiperspectivity” (Freitag-Hild 2022, 113), which invites students to ask whose identities are represented, whose are silenced, and how cultural or social positioning shapes these depictions.

- The Diversity domain (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3) aligns with “creating irritation” (Freitag-Hild 2022, 113), a strategy that evokes discomfort, raises awareness, and uses respectful language when encountering biased or stereotypical portrayals.
- The Justice domain (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3) resonates with “sociopolitical reflection” (Freitag-Hild 2022, 113-4), helping students interrogate the systematic power structures in conflicts, character hierarchies, or world-building.
- The Action domain (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3) relates to “fostering participation” (Freitag-Hild 2022, 114), prompting learners to transform awareness into agency in the real world.

3.3.2 Eder’s Clock of Character (2010) and Doelker’s Visual Literacy (2015)

While SJS and Critical Literacy provide scaffolding for themes and narratives in a series, the Clock of Character and Visual Literacy models lay out the tools to unpack how meaning is constructed in visual storytelling. Eder’s Clock of Character (2010) outlines what dimensions of character should be examined, while Doelker’s (2015) visual literacy model provides the tools to decode their visual representation across different semiotic layers.

- Step 1 of image reading, as defined by Doelker (2015)
The viewer perceives the image personally, shaped by their own experiences, associations, and emotions. This perception is strongly influenced by the individual’s personality and is subjective (Doelker 2015, 46).
- Step 2 of image reading, as defined by Doelker (2015)
The Artifact category, as defined by Eder (2010, 21), aligns with the second step of image reading by Doelker (2015, 46), which looks at the inherent meaning of a visual element. They both address the formal elements of visual design that shape character representation, like costume, camera angle, lighting, and gesture. The Fictional Being dimension (Eder 2010, 21) looks at how a character acts and behaves and their relations in a fictional world. The Symbol dimension (Eder 2010, 21) mirrors the fixed and latent meaning of Doelker’s eight semantic layers (2015, 45), helping the viewer understand how character representation embodies abstract concepts like justice, freedom, or resistance.

- Step 3 of image reading, as defined by Doelker (2015)

The Symptom dimension (Eder 2010, 21) is deepened by declarative, contextual, intertextual, and transtextual semantic layers of visual decoding (Doelker 2015, 45; see Section 2.4.4), and it shows how characters serve as reflections or critiques of broader societal issues, as well as examining the intended meaning.

3.3.3 Doering's Affective-Cognitive Theory (2013) in Dialogue with Eder (2010), Doelker (2015), and SJS (2022)

While Eder and Doelker look at the representation of characters and the construction of meaning in media, Doering focuses on audience reception and how students relate to characters emotionally and psychologically. This is particularly important for anti-bias education, as it combines analytical distance with emotional and personal connection.

- Empathy (Doering 2013, 97) links to Eder's "Fictional Being" as students emotionally identify with a character's inner world and challenges.
- Identification (Doering 2013, 305-6), on both visual and narrative levels, intersects with step 2 of image reading, providing insight into why students may feel close or repelled by certain character representations.
- Social comparison (Doering 2013, 300) draws on SJS's Identity and Diversity domains and Doelker's contextual layer as students reflect on how characters' lives mirror or differ from their own.
- Parasocial relationships (Doering 2013, 303), or the sense of connection with characters over time, link to the SJS's Action domain, as emotional investment can catalyse student motivation for social engagement.

3.4 Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework

Building on the theoretical foundations previously outlined, this section presents the Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework developed specifically for this study. The structure is composed of five broad categories: Visual Scene Decoding, Identity, Diversity, Justice, and Action, which serve as entry points for deeper inquiry and reflection. These domains are further expanded through principles of Critical Literacy (McLaughlin and DeVoogd 2004; Freitag-Hild 2022), which help unpack issues of representation power, Doelker’s (2015) visual literacy, which offers a method for analysing visual and semi-otic elements, Eder’s (2010) Clock of Character provides a method to examine character construction, and at last, Doering’s (2013) affective-cognitive theory, which explains how learners emotionally connect and relate to character representation and how this engagement can lead to meaningful reflection or action.

These categories translate the theory, along with a few additions by the author, into concrete analytical prompts suitable for research and adaptable for classroom use (see Chapter 6), directly addressing RQ1 and RQ3. This framework will be used in the later stages of the analysis of *Avatar: The Last Airbender* and will enable the findings to be explicitly and systematically linked back to these foundational theories.

Table 1: Synthesised Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework

<p>Visual Scene Decoder How do the visuals shape interpretation?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Immediate gut reaction to the scene? (Doelker 2015: Spontaneous meaning) 2. What is literally depicted? (Doelker: Denotative meaning) 3. What mood or atmosphere is conveyed? (Doelker: Latent meaning) 4. What were the creator’s intention and how does that affect interpretation? (Doelker: Intended meaning)
<p>Identity How are identities constructed and represented?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What information about the character’s personal, cultural, and social identity (race, gender, class, language, etc.) is presented? (Eder 2010: Fictional Being) How do these interact or conflict? 2. How are these identities made visible or invisible through audiovisual choices (e.g., costume, voice, framing)? (Doelker: Denotative/Expressive)

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. How does language shape identity (word choice, formality, accent, self-expression) (Freitag Hild 2022: Critical Literacy) 4. What does the character represent (values, struggles, ideologies, socially, politically, emotionally)? (Eder: Symbol) 5. Does the character challenge or reinforce stereotypes? (Freitag Hild: Creating Irritation) 6. How does the character view themselves and how are they perceived by others? Are there contradictions or internal conflicts? (SJS 2022: Identity) 7. With whom do viewers identify, and why? (Doering 2013: Identification + Empathy)
<p>Diversity How are differences portrayed and what interactions do they create?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How are relationships across different social groups (e.g., nations, cultures, abilities, ages) portrayed? Are individuals shown beyond group labels? What might be missing? (Freitag Hild: Multiperspectivity) 2. Does the character express pride in their identity and respect for others? (SJS: Diversity) 3. How do characters navigate between different social, cultural, or community spaces? (SJS: Diversity) 4. Are differences shown as enriching, problematic, or threatening? 5. How does the visual design signal inclusion, exclusion, or hierarchy? (Doelker: Symbolic/Latent Meaning) 6. How would the story change if told from another character's point of view or set in a different time or culture? (Freitag-Hild: multiperspectivity) 7. Did any moments challenge existing assumptions or generate discomfort? (Freitag Hild: Irritation) 8. How do viewers compare their own background and experiences (ethnicity, gender, sexuality, class, age, religion etc.) with those of the characters? (Doering: Social Comparison)
<p>Justice What power structures are shown and how are they challenged?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What forms of bias or injustices (e.g., discrimination, war, imperialism, inequality) are present, and what are their consequences? (SJS: Justice) 2. Who benefits from or holds power? How do they use or lose it? (Freitag Hild: Sociopolitical reflection) 3. Whose perspective dominates the story? Whose voices are missing or marginalized? (Freitag-Hild: Multiperspectivity; SJS: Justice)

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. How are systems of oppression visually encoded (e.g., language, architecture, uniforms, lighting, space)? (Doelker: Contextual + Transtextual Layers) 5. What broader social and political conflicts or ideologies (e.g., racism, imperialism, classism) do the characters symbolise? (Eder: Symptom + Symbol) 6. What emotional reactions did these injustices evoke in the viewer? (Doering: Empathy)
<p>Action What responses to injustice are modelled?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do characters resist injustice or act for change? What skills, values, or mindsets (empathy, responsibility, agency) help them? (Freitag Hild: Participation; SJS: Action) 2. What are the risks and consequences of speaking out? 3. How are fairness, protest, or resistance expressed visually or verbally? (Eder: Fictional Being + Artifact) 4. Are there examples of collective action or allyship? What strategies are used, and how effective are they? (SJS: Action) 5. What narrative or visual cues suggest transformation or hope (e.g., inspirational scenes, colour shifts, music)? (Doelker: Articulated/Latent) 6. How might the viewers interpretation inspire action or reflection? (Doering: Parasocial Relationships + Agency)

3.5 Researcher Positionality

As acknowledged in Chapter 1, this research is influenced by my long personal connection to *A:TLA* and by an interest in anti-bias education and inclusive teaching. Such positionality, as well as the familiarity with the series, my background in art history, and interest in pop culture, can deepen the attention to subtle audiovisual motifs, emotional arcs, and issues of representation.

However, this also introduces potential biases. Long-term familiarity with the series and being subjected to two decades of discourse around *A:TLA* may heighten empathy towards certain characters and actions. Likewise, my orientation towards identifying patterns and pedagogical potential may predispose me to highlight certain themes that aren't that prominent.

3.6 Procedure

The analytical process followed an iterative, theory-informed cycle, combining deductive and inductive reasoning. It was done in the following five stages.

Stage 1: Familiarization and Scene Selection

Episodes were viewed to segment and identify key moments featuring Zuko. The specific core episodes were chosen based on their thematic relevance to the four anti-bias goals, their significance to Zuko's character development, and their potential for classroom discussion. During renewed watching, detailed notes were taken, laying the groundwork for future analysis.

Stage 2: Visual Scene Decoder (VSD)

Each episode was first examined through the Visual Scene Decoder (VSD), based on Doelker's (2015) three steps of image reading. This stage captures initial impressions and surface-level visual and emotional cues, serving as a scaffolding step that grounds later stages of deep analysis. In a classroom setting, VSD plays a central role, where only a few scenes might be analysed, and subjective responses take on a bigger role. However, in this study, because of the scope of the material, it serves primarily as a pre-analytical foundation grounding later interpretations of the IDJA dimensions.

Stage 3: IDJA Inquiry

Each episode was analysed through the lens of the Identity, Diversity, Justice, and Action dimensions, using prompts from the synthesised anti-bias media analysis framework. This stage unpacks how meaning is constructed. In these dimensions, character coding (Eder 2010) and the affective-cognitive layers (Doering 2013) are also identified and explored. Character coding draws on how visuals, sound, and performance contribute to character symbolism and complexity. The affective-cognitive layer anticipated how viewers might react to the character and how that might influence classroom discussion and interpretation. While answering the prompts, some questions turned out to be insignificant, while others didn't address aspects of the show that needed further examination. Thus, changes to the framework and its prompts were made to meet its demands.

Stage 4: Cross-Episode Synthesis

Findings from each episode are brought together in a cross-episode synthesis across the four IDJA domains. Answers from the prompts were examined for similarities, differences, and changes to trace shifts in Zuko's representation and transformation, addressing RQ2.

Stage 5: Theoretical Integration Pedagogical Translation

The analytical insights were connected back to the theoretical foundations and were translated into pedagogical takeaways. These takeaways included ideas for the design of classroom applications that integrate anti-bias education through watching *A:TLA*. In the next chapter, the analytical outcomes were transformed into concrete teaching tools for general application. This final step addresses RQ3 by demonstrating how the framework can shape inclusive, critical, and transferable teaching practices in secondary EFL contexts.

3.7 Summary

This chapter has outlined a qualitative, critical multimodal approach for analysing representation and social issues in *A:TLA*. By combining deductive and inductive reasoning, the analysis balances theoretical structure with interpretative openness, enabling a nuanced understanding of how media operates. The next chapter will present the findings of this analysis and demonstrate how the adapted framework operates in practice.

4. Critical Analysis

This chapter presents the main findings of the critical multimodal analysis of Zuko in *Avatar: The Last Airbender*, based on the synthesised anti-bias media analysis framework developed in Chapter 3. The analyses are based on four key episodes: The Storm (S1E12), Zuko Alone (S2E7), The Crossroads of Destiny (S2E20), and The Western Air Temple (S3E12), which are documented in detail in the episode analysis sheets (see Appendix A-D).

The analysis will directly address RQ2 by showing how character representation in *A:TLA* models anti-bias themes in an accessible way and demonstrates how they are constructed through audiovisual elements and narrative choices. The following sections synthesise patterns across episodes, highlighting how the framework foregrounds different themes that will later be connected to anti-bias education and pedagogical implications in the Discussion chapter.

4.1 Identity: From stereotypical villain to conflicted subject

A key first finding is how the show makes Zuko's shift from a one-dimensional antagonist to a highly conflicted protagonist. His first leitmotif is dominated by horns, brass, and drums signalling aggression and rigidity. A leitmotif is a "recurring musical theme" used to present a particular character, emotion, or concept in a work (Britannica Editors 2025). His line "You better learn respect, or I'll teach it to you" (The Storm, 04:55-05:07) marks his abrasive and authoritarian language and is further framed by sharp camera angles and red lighting (Appendix A, VSD, Identity). Through the Identity and Diversity categories, viewers would initially read Zuko as a stereotypical villain, as he is a male, royal, hostile, militarised teenager obsessed with honour and pursuing the hero.

However, the Identity and Justice dimensions for "The Storm" (Appendix A) destabilise this stereotype. The flashback to the duel between his father and him positions him as a victim, as he was met with humiliation, exile, and a scar on his face. Here, the prompts on self-perception, internal conflict, and systemic injustice come together as

Zuko's scar is marked as both a personal trauma and a visible sign of the Fire Nation's authoritarianism. Viewers' interpretation of him starts to shift here.

In "Zuko Alone" the framework highlights how his identity is further complicated by displacement. Coding under the Identity and Diversity (Appendix B) domains, note how his royal status is visually stripped away (peasant clothes, hat hiding his face) while the flashback scenes depict a once-privileged childhood, shaped by war talk, parental conflicts, and increasing pressure to conform to the nation. Zuko becomes a figure of the in-between (Bhabha [1994] 2012), where he is no longer at home in the Fire Nation, yet not trusted by the Earth Kingdom villagers either. His identity changes depending on who the people around him perceive him as: a threat, a lonely young man, or a disappointing son.

In "The Crossroads of Destiny" the Action and Justice categories (Appendix C) capture his ambivalence at the "crossroads". Zuko is offered two competing choices: siding with his uncle Iroh, who embodies compassion and transformation, and his little sister Azula, who represents the Fire Nation's ideologies. His decision to side with Azula, despite the intimacy and empathy he had built in the crystal cave with the supposed "enemy," Katara, shows that change is not linear and that the desire for his father's approval overrides moral decision-making.

Finally in "The Western Air Temple" the Identity and Action dimension (Appendix D) coding document Zuko's attempt to re-introduce himself by his awkward apology "I thought I was good before, but now I realise I was bad" (The Western Air Temple, 05:35-06:07), his willingness to kneel and be taken a prisoner, and his explicit redefinition honour as moral agency shows his vulnerability, self-awareness and transformation.

The four episodes together across a three-season-long arc show, with the help of the framework, the tension between how Zuko sees himself, how others see him, and how imperial ideology has shaped both sides. He is portrayed as a young person negotiating trauma, loyalty, and moral growth in shifting social contexts.

4.2 Diversity: Relationships

The Diversity dimension emphasises how relationships across nations, classes, and ages function as sites of both prejudice and empathy (see Diversity Sections in Appendix A-D). Zuko's relationships with others play a central role in understanding his identity and potential for change. They illustrate how trust, prejudice, and empathy shift depending on history, context, and personal experience.

4.2.1 Zuko, Iroh, and the Fire Nation Crew

Tension between the "spoiled prince" and ordinary Fire Nation soldiers in "The Storm" (Appendix A, Diversity) exposes internal class hierarchies within the supposed unified Fire Nation. Iroh serves as a bridge when he softens conflicts and advocates for Zuko. Iroh thus models a different kind of leadership than that of the authoritarian Fire Lord. This tension shows that Zuko is actually not surrounded by blind support but is often met with scepticism. Iroh is the only person who understands and accepts him for who he is, even when he disagrees with his actions, because he believes that there is still good in Zuko.

4.2.2 Zuko and the Earth Kingdom Family

In "Zuko Alone" (Appendix B, Diversity), the framework captures a rare moment of intimacy across enemy lines between Zuko and the Earth Kingdom family. Zuko teaches the son swordplay in the barn, shares meals, and is being seen as an older brother figure rather than "the enemy". Zuko also feels a sense of familial security he hasn't felt since his mother disappeared. Diversity coding stresses how war identities (Fire Nation Prince, Earth Kingdom soldiers) collide with everyday identities (parent, sibling), inviting viewers to think about individuals beyond group labels.

4.2.3 Zuko and Katara

The crystal cave scene (Appendix C, Diversity) is seen as a climactic moment for Zuko and Katara, where they both show empathy for each other. They both share experiences of losing parents and war trauma. Katara's line about violence being "in his blood"

(The Crossroads of Destiny, 08:15-32) reflects the difficulty of seeing beyond inherited identities, which can be critically examined through the framework's prompts on challenging stereotypes, irritation, and changing perspectives. Zuko is forced to think beyond just himself and has to be confronted yet again with the real consequences of war, which marks an emotional and moral turning point for him.

4.2.4 Zuko and the Gaang

"The Western Air Temple" highlights how the different upbringings of the group's members shape their positions on Zuko. Katara, who experienced great loss at the hands of the Fire Nation, is justifiably mistrusting of him. Toph, who grew up privileged and was sheltered from the war yet is blind and has to trust her instincts all the time, acts as the advocate who recognises his sincerity. And at last, Aang, with his pacifist upbringing and his role as the Avatar, who has to bring balance to the world, is the undecided mediator. The Diversity domain (Appendix C) helps to get to the surface how trust-building after harm is complex, and how each character's prior experiences shape opinions. Across the episodes, Zuko and the Gaang are coded as a multicultural, differently abled group. Their diversity in the show is shown as unexpected and a bit strange, yet their bond is shown as something genuine and natural.

4.3 Injustice: Audiovisual coding of power and trauma

Another major pattern is how strong audiovisual elements like physical places, colour palettes, lighting, musical leitmotifs, and physical appearance encode systems of power and oppression. The Visual Scene Decoder, combined with Justice prompts, makes these scenes explicit for viewers (see VSD and Justice sections in Appendix A-D). These patterns show how the adapted framework helps students move beyond plot to interrogate how meaning is constructed.

4.3.1 Throne rooms and palaces

In "The Storm" and "Zuko Alone" the Fire Nation throne room is depicted as vast, dark, and imposing. The distant, faceless Fire Lord is surrounded by fire, emphasising cold

authority and emotional absence. Towering pillars, elevated thrones, and symmetrical layouts create a sense of untouchable power. The notes in the Justice and VSD Domains (Appendix A and B) describe these design elements as metaphors for dehumanisation, intimidation, and absolute power. The coronation of Ozai (Appendix B, VSD) is explicitly described as echoing fascist aesthetics. The uniformed crowds, display of big flags, and the use of fire as a spectacle all invite comparisons to real-world authoritarian regimes within the Justice dimension and show that Zuko is in an environment where obedience is demanded and expected.

4.3.2 Colour palettes and lighting

Flashbacks in both “The Storm” and “Zuko Alone” showcase the Fire Nation royal palace, which is drenched in reds and golds signalling wealth, power, militarism, and danger, while Earth Kingdom villages are coded in dusty and washed-out greens to convey scarcity and neglect (Appendix A and B, VSD, Justice). In “The Crossroads of Destiny” the warm and sunlit outside of the Earth King’s court contrasts sharply with the dark, green-tinted palace interior once Azula’s coup starts (Appendix C, Identity, Justice). The shift visually shows Zuko’s inner turmoil between choosing a peaceful, ordinary life or returning back to violent power structures.

4.3.3 Musical leitmotifs

Music mirrors Zuko’s emotional state. Zuko’s early scenes are accompanied by imposing brass and drums, which signify anger and determination. When he returned to Fire Nation, his leitmotif also reflected his betrayal (Appendix C, Action). And in the later scenes, especially “The Western Air Temple” a softer, more hesitant leitmotif is used that matches his vulnerability (Appendix D, VSD). The analysis shows how music becomes a cue for viewers to read character development and moral positioning.

4.3.4 Scars

Zuko’s scar is repeatedly identified as an important symbol where personal and systemic violence intersect (Appendix A-D, Identity and Justice). It is a symbol of shame

as everybody knows he got it from his father, making him instantly recognisable across the nations. But it also shows that any disagreement with the Fire Lord is met with severe punishment. Katara's offer to heal it in "The Crossroads of Destiny" (Appendix C) is coded as a potential act of reconciliation. His refusal shows how trauma cannot be undone purely through magic or good intentions and requires internal work.

Throughout the episodes, audiovisual elements constantly externalise Zuko's emotional struggles and the oppressive environments shaping him. Throne rooms reflect domination and authoritarianism, colours distinguish class, music signals inner conflict, and the scar makes trauma visible. These multimodal cues help the viewers recognise that Zuko's journey is shaped as much by structures around him as well as by his own choices.

4.4 Action: Resistance and Transformation

Across the episodes, in the Justice and especially in the Action dimensions, the tension between resistance and complicity is highlighted, showing that change and "correct" moral decision-making are not straightforward or easy.

4.4.1 Speaking up carries risks

In "The Storm" (Appendix A, Justice, Action) Zuko's first act of resistance, which was questioning the plan to sacrifice an entire army division, resulted in him getting physically and mentally scarred and exiled from his home nation. This incident showed how systems punish those who show empathy or question authority. In "Zuko Alone" (Appendix B, Action), when Zuko confronted the corrupt soldiers, he again put himself in physical danger and faced social rejection after his Fire Nation identity was revealed. Even when he tried to explain himself in "The Western Air Temple," he expected to be dismissed by the Gaang (Appendix D, Action). While the first two incidents scarred him and are one of the reasons for his complicity in war, the last incident showed growth and vulnerability.

4.4.2 Complicity

Even as Zuko resists specific injustices, he still benefits from imperial structures and actively participates in harmful actions. He hunts down the Avatar with help from the military, hires assassins, and asserts dominance through his bending powers and title (Appendix A Justice; D Action). Structural injustices like war, imperialism, and power abuse are always present in the story but not explicitly mentioned by name. Zuko's arc shows that while individual choices matter, they are constrained by history, family, and ideologies. It shows how hard it is to challenge a system that shaped one's entire sense of self.

The symbolism used to convey this fractured identity and the push-and-pull between complicity and conscience is most clearly exemplified in a scene from "The Crossroads of Destiny". In that scene ("The Crossroads of Destiny", 16.03-16.06), chiaroscuro lighting splits his face between his scarred side and the illuminated "normal" side of his face. Chiaroscuro lighting is a visual arts element in which a stark contrast between dark and light creates a dramatic effect that heightens emotional tension (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica 2025).

4.4.3 Non-linear change

"The Crossroads of Destiny" (Appendix C, Action) is central here. The farmwork's focus on "risks and consequences of speaking out" and "creator's intention" helps frame his betrayal in this episode not just as a plot twist but as an example of how trauma and the promise of belonging can pull someone back into harmful patterns. His arc is full of ups and downs, as he learns so much but makes just as many mistakes. Only in the middle of the last season, after a long time, support, and emotional reflective work, did Zuko show true transformation.

4.4.4 Redefining honour and choosing agency

Zuko's apology speech to the Gaang is coded as a crystallisation of his moral learning: "no one can give you honour, it's something you earn for yourself by choosing to do what's right" (The Western Air Temple, 19:56-20:27; Appendix D Action). The soft

lighting and the music underscore the sincerity of this moment. His decision to join the Gaang and use firebending for protection rather than domination embodies the Action dimension's emphasis on agency, responsibility, and participation. Zuko denouncing the Fire Nation's actions and taking accountability for his past makes him seem less performative because he proposes genuine change.

4.5 Summary

The episode analysis shows that the tension between personal identity, social expectations, and systems of power shapes Zuko's arc. The audiovisual elements show the complexity of his inner world and the harsh outside world he lives in. His relationships illustrate how trust and prejudice operate across cultural and national boundaries. His journey from complicity to self-defined honour shows that moral agency is complex and non-linear. These findings provide the basis for the Discussion chapter, where they will be explicitly connected to previously discussed theory, anti-bias education, and classroom applications for the secondary EFL contexts.

5. Discussion

This chapter interprets the findings of the multimodal analysis through a pedagogical lens, focusing on how Zuko's character arc in *Avatar: The Last Airbender* can support anti-bias competences in the secondary EFL classroom. It first synthesises analytical insights across the IDJA domains, then examines how visual storytelling can serve as an entry point to anti-bias learning, and finally discusses implications for Swiss secondary EFL contexts. It also evaluates the strengths and challenges of applying the framework and connects the results to the study's research questions.

5.1 Overview of Key Findings Across IDJA Domains and Interpretation in Relation to Anti-Bias Education

In relation to RQ2, the analysis demonstrated that *A:TLA* offers a multimodal space for learners to engage with anti-bias concepts. Across the four episodes, Zuko models processes that are central to anti-bias education: identity formation, intercultural learning, recognising structural injustice, and taking action in the form of moral agency. The results show that Zuko's arc can serve as a powerful example for the IDJA domains by making complex social issues more accessible and discussable.

5.1.1 Identity

Zuko's journey disrupts fixed identity categories, revealing identity as an evolving negotiation between personal history, relationships, and the social norms that shape a person. His shifting visual and narrative presentation across the episodes reflects Hall's (1996, 4) notion of identity as "becoming" rather than "being". The series makes the complexity of characters visible rather than resorting to stereotypical portrayals. It does so by depicting character arcs that encompass multiple, sometimes conflicting, dimensions, which cannot be boxed into a single category.

Through Zuko's transformation, the series showed how identity is shaped by trauma, privilege, and socialisation. This aligns with the Social Justice Standards (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3) Identity domain as it focuses on developing positive self-concepts while

critically interacting with the ways different social and cultural memberships shape how people see themselves and others. The representation encourages learners to interrogate their own and others' identities beyond labels.

5.1.2 Diversity

Zuko's relationships across nations, classes, and ages illuminate how difference is navigated in moments of conflict and solidarity. Encounters with his uncle Iroh, the Earth Kingdom Family, Katara, and the Gaang reveal how prejudice, empathy, and belonging shape how relationships across differences are built. These encounters in these character constellations (Eder 2010) show the intersection of everyday roles (mentor, child, friend) with prescribed war identities. In these moments, Zuko moves through the "in-between" (Bhabha [1994] 2012, 2), where he is reconfiguring his self through contact with others. As Saurer (2019, 41) described, it was only after Zuko was displaced from home and was confronted with unfamiliar surroundings that he started to rethink his worldview and appreciate other people and nations.

This aligns with the SJS's Diversity domain, which emphasises respecting and valuing diversity, using accurate language, and building empathy and understanding across social boundaries (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3; Derman-Sparks 1989, 6). In *A:TLA* diversity is also encoded in its blended spaces (Fauconnier and Turner 2003), multicultural world-building, and by challenging binary distinctions such as good/evil or enemy/ally through its character constellations.

5.1.3 Justice

In *A:TLA* justice is deeply embedded in the narrative and audiovisual designs, such as the architecture, colour design, and leitmotifs. Through the red-black colour palette, hard angles, and militaristic composition, which are all semantic layers (Doelker 2015) of the Fire Nation, viewers can literally see the mechanisms of propaganda, cult of personality, nationalism, and authoritarianism. Justice is not a simple matter of overthrowing a "villain" but interrogating how systemic structures uphold hierarchy and imperialism.

Kerr (2024, 1024) emphasises this shift in attention from individual villains to the structures that sustain domination. For an anti-bias classroom, this distinction is crucial. As shown in Zuko's arc, individual good deeds do not necessarily lead to a change of harmful systems as extreme nationalism (Audi 2009) and its traits override the well-being of humanity at large. Derman-Sparks (1989, 8) reminds educators that individuals, just like Zuko, may revert to internalised hierarchies when confronted with discomfort or fear. Zuko, after a long process, begins to see the injustice in the world, mostly caused by the Fire Nation, and realises he, as a former perpetrator, must challenge them.

Everything mentioned above aligns with the Justice domain of the Social Justice Standards, which focuses on recognising unfairness, understanding how systemic inequalities operate, and being able to challenge them (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3; Derman-Sparks and Edwards 2010, 5). Freitag-Hild (2022, 109) further emphasises that critical literacy requires moving beyond moral judgment ("Zuko is bad") to sociopolitical inquiry ("How does the Fire Nation's ideology justify violence?").

5.1.4 Action

The Action domain within the Social Justice Standards calls for turning awareness into concrete action. Students "take action when [they] see unfairness in [their] everyday lives" and "stand up for [themselves] and others" (Chiariello et al. 2022, 9). Similarly, Derman-Sparks (1989, 3) emphasises that simply being an observer isn't good enough and that active interventions against all forms of oppression make one anti-bias.

Zuko's developments from speaking up, failing, relapsing, and seeking accountability illustrate the non-linear nature of moral agency. This also reflects research showing that moral agency develops through an iterative process, social context, feedback, and missteps (Montreuil et al. 2018, 21-22). His transformation offers a realistic model for anti-bias action, which requires individuals to interrupt oppressive patterns and behaviours in themselves (Derman-Sparks 1989, 3) and recognise their "own responsibility to stand up to exclusion, prejudice, and injustice" (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3).

The Gaang's gradual, conditional acceptance illustrates that change is relational, as those who were harmed are not obligated to forgive immediately, and trust must be rebuilt over time. They expect non-performative (Kutlaca and Radke 2022) and non-tokenistic (Kanter 1977) actions from Zuko, as they only knew him as someone who only did things that served his quests. This mirrors Derman-Sparks' (1989, 8) insight that anti-bias action carries social risk and is not automatically rewarded. Learners see through Zuko how "standing up" can be done by showing small interventions, sincere apologies, intentional inclusion (Luder 2017), and sustained, genuine behavioural change.

5.2 Pedagogical Implications

In relation to RQ2, the findings suggest that Zuko's character representation in *Avatar: The Last Airbender* can be used as a multimodal classroom resource. The following sections illustrate how the show supports anti-bias learning.

5.2.1 Developing Media Literacy

Zuko's evolving identity provides a basis through which learners can explore and compare different identity concepts, moments of belonging or exclusion, with their own experiences. By viewing characters as symbols, artifacts, and symptoms (Eder 2010), and by practising describing audiovisual elements such as colour, framing, and leitmotifs within a picture's semantic layer (Doelker 2015), students can create meaning. This supports the development of media literacy (Suess et al. 2018, 116), social awareness (Derman-Sparks 1989, 3), and empathy (Doering 2013, 299), and encourages students to reflect on how real identities are formed, challenged, and changed by unpacking how fictional identities are brought to life in stories.

5.2.2 Supporting Intercultural Understanding

Zuko's in-between (Bhabha [1994] 2012) position resonates with students navigating multilingual or multicultural identities. His relationships with others model moments of conflict and reconciliation, providing a start for discussions about belonging, prejudice,

and cultural negotiation. Such conversations directly serve the Social Justice Standards of building empathy and understanding across differences (Chiariello et al. 2022, 3). By confronting moments of discomfort, students practice perspective taking, question dominant and marginalised voices (Freitag-Hild 2022, 113), and learn how to “respond to differences”, which are all essential competences in anti-bias education (Derman-Sparks 1989, 6).

5.2.3 Engagement with Complex Topics

Fictional worlds allow students to explore themes such as nationalism, loss, propaganda, and discrimination without the emotional and political weight of real-world examples. This supports age-appropriate exploration of bias and injustice, while allowing the teacher to scaffold discussions safely.

For example, a multimodal analysis of the depiction of the Fire Nation, which draws on Imperial Japan, can help students identify how power relations, propaganda, and nationalism are produced and normalised. Students are invited to consider why moral actions may fail under structural pressure, how individuals become both agents and victims of systemic violence, and the similarities they see in the current world. By supporting learners to question social structures and develop the critical skills needed to actively intervene against institutions that perpetuate oppression, teachers uphold humanitarian and democratic values of being a teacher in Switzerland (Lehrplan 21, 2017).

5.2.4 Promoting Moral Agency

Zuko’s arc illustrates that anti-bias action requires self-reflection, risk-taking, and a willingness to confront internalised beliefs. The analysis shows that the series doesn’t immediately redeem Zuko after one good deed, that trust must be rebuilt, apologies must be sincere, and actions must be consistent. This discrepancy between why viewers want to forgive Zuko way sooner than the Gaang should be addressed and could be explained through the concept of parasocial relationships (Doering 2013, 305).

From an affective-cognitive view (Doering 2013, 305) the audience's frustration with Zuko can function as a learning affect. In the classroom, analysing his relapse can prompt discussions about peer pressure, conformity, and the non-linear nature of moral agency, which resonate with teenagers' own negotiation of autonomy. In the classroom, Zuko's narrative offers students a mirror to reflect on their own positions, biases, and capacities for change. Students can practice moral agency and accountability by comparing fictional and real instances of unfairness and proposing small, realistic responses that lead to meaningful action.

5.3 Strengths and Challenges of the Framework

Applying the synthesised framework to four episodes revealed several strengths. The IDJA domains ensure that questions of Identity, Diversity, Justice, and Action are in the foreground rather than treated as optional. At the same time, the boundaries between these domains are blurred and deeply intertwined both in the series and in the real world. Rather than seeing this as a drawback, this overlap should be seen as an opportunity to discuss how the dimensions of anti-bias work are inseparable.

The VSD is a good anchor for concrete audiovisual details such as colour, framing, music, gesture, and feeling. This is a scaffold for when students are later confronted with more abstract IDJA questions to get their feelings and facts in order. Even though it can be hard to differentiate which details are important, the VSD functions as a starting point for moving from observations to producing meaning.

The combination of IDJA prompts with character coding and affective-cognitive layers constantly prompts one to think about how a character is symbolically coded, how viewers are guided to feel, and how those feelings can be questioned through concepts like irritation. This prevented the analysis from focusing solely on plot or solely on ideology. However, there is a risk of over-interpretation because analysis could lead to attributing intention to design choices that are conventional rather than symbolic.

Implementing the same set of prompts across four different episodes helps with pattern recognition over time, such as shifts in leitmotifs, evolving relationships, setbacks, and recurring injustices. Although using the same questions can get repetitive, especially

given how much the domains overlap, the framework lends itself well for cross-episode analysis.

One of the big challenges is that applying the full framework demands a lot from teachers, as it requires experience with multimodal analysis, media and visual literacy, and knowledge of sensitive social subjects and how to address them in the classroom. Consequently, the framework can also be demanding for students, who have to juggle multiple forms of analysis.

5.4 Summary in Relation to the Research Questions

This chapter synthesised how Zuko's arc mirrors ABE goals and offers pedagogical takeaways for discussions of bias, empathy, power, and moral agency. Zuko's narrative demonstrates how learners can analyse and engage with complex character journeys in fictional media to support anti-bias development and foster inclusive learning environments, thereby addressing RQ2.

The findings confirm that, as discussed in chapters 3.3 and 3.4 and in relation to RQ1, synthesising IDJA with critical literacy, visual literacy, character theory, and affective-cognitive theory allowed the study to develop a tool that enables multimodal interpretation and engagement with visual storytelling and character representation. This tool encourages viewers to move beyond just plot reading, offering a structured yet flexible approach to anti-bias education. The framework constantly highlights power, complex identities, and actions that seek for a better world, while still leaving room for viewer interpretations and real-world transfer.

In response to RQ3, the framework is transferable beyond *A:TLA*, as the same prompts and anti-bias concepts can be applied to other films, series, and graphic novels. The framework provides the scaffolding for any media in which the takeaway messages are anti-bias oriented. Different approaches to transferability will be explored in more detail in the next chapter.

6. Practical Application

Building on the insights from the Discussions chapter, this chapter outlines how *A:TLA* and Zuko’s arc, in particular, can be used in the secondary EFL classrooms to foster media literacy and anti-bias competences. The chapter presents the Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework, discusses guiding principles for its general classroom use, and provides concrete ideas and activities organised by the IDJA domains for *A:TLA*. The aim is not to give rigid lesson plans but to offer flexible structures that teachers can adapt to different age groups and proficiency levels. Other resources for implementing anti-bias education in the classroom are available on the Learning for Justice website.

The Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework diagram below visualises a simplified version of the framework. At the centre is the Visual Scene Decoder (VSD), surrounded by the four IDJA domains. Each segment contains key analytical prompts. The diagram illustrates that anti-bias media literacy is interconnected. Analysis can begin at any point and often will move back and forth between dimensions. Teachers may hang up the diagram in the classroom for constant visual reference. Appendix F includes a scaffolded and a blank version that can be used as a note-taking sheet during viewing activities.

Figure 1: Anti-Bias Media Analysis Diagram. Design elements sourced from ©Sabina Alcaraz via Canva.com

6.1 Guiding Principles for Classroom Use

The following principles provide a foundation for implementing the Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework in the EFL classroom. They highlight how media analysis can become a training ground for broader anti-bias media literacy competences, helping students use English to communicate, interpret, question, and develop the skills to act in a pluralistic world. All of the following guidelines and activities are based on the previous interpretations and analysis, as well as the author's own experience as a teacher.

- **What is Anti-Bias Education?**

Before applying the framework, learners should be introduced to key ideas from Learning for Justice's Social Justice Standards (Chiariello et al. 2022). By briefly reviewing the four IDJA domains, new vocabulary and concepts are anchored, and a common understanding of these domains is established for future classroom discussion. This orientation should be done in the beginning and then revisited throughout the process as needed. Hanging up posters that outline the goals of each domain could provide students with a visual reminder of the principles of anti-bias education.

- **Move from perception -> interpretation -> reflection -> action**

Having a consistent watching structure helps students maintain a stable routine whenever they work with a scene or an episode. By following these next four stages, lessons gain a rhythm in which students know what to expect and how to approach new content.

Before watching a scene or an episode, the teacher should point out one or two domains for the students to focus on. It prevents the students from being overwhelmed by all the prompts and keeps the watching process intentional. In between the steps of interpretation and reflection, there can be many different tasks and activities implemented, which can foster understanding and create meaning. The Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework should be adapted for each viewing experience and can be deepened with questions from the original framework (see Table 1), but in short, the following steps provide a basic sequence to follow:

1. Perception: What do you see/feel?

Following the VSD domain, this first step is all about first impressions. Students observe narratively, visually, and emotionally what is present in the scene, like characters, sounds, and plot points, without needing to interpret anything. This step grounds everyone in the same starting point.

2. Interpretation: How and why does the scene create meaning? (multi-modal/character analysis)

In the second step, using the pre-decided IDJA domains, students make sense of what they have observed. They look at how the scenes use audiovisual elements to shape meaning and explore a character's symbolic function, motivation, relationships, and tensions.

3. Reflection: What issues of identity, diversity, justice, and action are involved?

This third step moves from interpretation to the social layers of IDJA. Students consider what the scene implies about identity, difference, power, bias, or injustice. The interpretation and reflection steps are closely intertwined, as students can engage with the IDJA domains in a meaningful way after a grounded analysis.

4. Action: Why does this matter, and might we do?

The final step is about turning interpretation into relevance. In the classroom, there should be links to everyday life, school dynamics, and social issues that they recognise. Action does not have to mean revolution, but can lead students to develop social awareness, moral agency, and empathy. This can be done in small steps, such as recognising a stereotype or offering support.

- **Watch whole episodes, but analyse “pressure point” scenes**

Full episodes provide necessary narrative contexts. However, analysis should happen in selected short “pressure point” scenes, where important moments of a character's arc are concentrated. These scenes, while seemingly short, are substantial enough for an IDJA-based analysis.

This method is transferable to most media, as all films, series, commercials, and video games contain pressure points. When teachers identify these moments and frame them with the anti-bias media analysis prompts, the workload becomes lighter. Teacher prompts and inputs should support exploration rather than dictate interpretation, but they should be done with intention so as not to lead students astray. Students don't need to answer all prompts from the framework at once. Selecting just two or three keeps the lesson focused. Guiding students to notice symbolism and nuance can broaden their understanding of narrative and representation.

- **Use characters as mirrors, windows, and models for moral agency**

Following Bishop's (2015) metaphor, windows allow students to learn about experiences different from their own, and mirrors allow students to recognise aspects of themselves in characters. Character representations provide a safe narrative distance while exploring themes of privilege, prejudice, and change. Every character's transformation, with all its progression and contradictions, should be shown as is, as a real journey of moral development, and invite students to reflect, share, or imagine comparable moments from everyday life. That's why it's important not to moralise characters as purely good or bad. Teachers can invite parallels by asking questions: "Has anyone experienced something similar or on a smaller scale?" or "What choices does this character have, and how might we relate to those choices?". This approach supports empathy and perspective-taking.

- **Media-specific Considerations**

Some stories deal with sensitive, complex themes such as war, trauma, abuse, or cultural appropriation. It should be pointed out that even if a show was made for children, it doesn't mean it can't tackle complex themes. These topics require care, but in connection with the chosen media, offer entry points for meaningful discussion if handled gently. Teachers have to pre-teach key vocabulary, offer content warnings, clarify cultural inspirations, and avoid stereotyping.

- **Link structural or real-world issues to concrete audiovisual cues**

Complex social concepts such as imperialism, nationalism, and misogyny should be anchored in recognisable audiovisual motifs (leitmotif, symbols, architecture, framing, clothing, language, ideologies) and simple vocabulary (power, rules, unfair, brave...).

Only then should discussions of these concepts be introduced and linked to real-world issues. It is an almost impossible ask to expect students to be able to make connections between audiovisual symbols and what they might stand for without teacher input, and this layered approach helps avoid confusion. Teachers should encourage students to question assumptions, imagine alternatives, and be controversial.

- **Integrate language scaffolds**

For meaningful, but not perfect, discussions, the classroom benefits from structured language scaffolds like:

- Sentence starters:

I think... because.../ From my point of view.../ This suggest that...

- Discussion starts(justification:

I agree/disagree because.../ Another interpretation might be...

- Emotion vocabulary:

Conflicted, overwhelmed, hopeful, determined, moody...

- Film language:

Background, camera angle, framing, music shift...

- IDJA specific:

Bias, power, fairness, privilege, identity, responsibility...

These support students' vocabulary range and enable nuanced interpretation even with limited linguistic resources.

6.2 Example Ideas for Using A:TLA in the Classroom

This section presents example aims and activities for each IDJA domain when working on Zuko's arc in *Avatar: The Last Airbender*. The following pressure point scenes, identified through the analysis earlier, are moments that invite deeper discussion in the classroom:

1. The Agni Kai in "The Storm" is a starting point for discussing identity, abuse, authoritarianism, and authoritarian parenting.
2. The effects of imperialism and fascist aesthetics in "Zuko Alone".
3. Katara's polarising statement, "it's in your blood," to discuss feeling empathy for the "villain" in "The Crossroads of Destiny".

4. The Gaang’s reluctance to forgive Zuko to discuss accountability in “The Western Air Temple”.

While the four analysed episodes capture Zuko’s essence and his journey through an anti-bias lens well, they cannot fully capture his character transformation. Because watching the entire series is impractical in a classroom setting, this focused selection offers a coherent arc without having to watch all 61 episodes. The additional episodes provide contextual support, even if they are not analysed in depth. They help students understand motivations and relationships that shape Zuko’s journey. Since one episode is on average twenty minutes long, it fits nicely into a 45-minute lesson. The highlighted episodes include the aforementioned pressure points, which should be analysed further.

Season 1	Season 2	Season 3
Episode 3 “The Southern Air Temple” Establishes Zuko’s early worldview and rivalry with Aang.	Episode 7 “Zuko Alone” Explores Zuko’s past and deepens his ideological doubts.	Episode 5 “The Beach” reveals Zuko’s inner turmoil and identity issues despite being welcomed back into the Fire Nation.
Episode 12 “The Storm” Reveals Zuko’s backstory and the origins of his internal conflict.	Episode 15 “The Tales of Ba Sing Se” Shows Zuko’s life as a normal teenager, and choosing kindness, signalling small growth.	Episode 11 “The Day of Black Sun, Part 2: The Eclipse” Show Zuko’s intentional break for the Fire Lord and the Fire Nation
Episode 13 “The Blue Spirit” Shows Zuko saving Aang in a disguise, hinting at his potential for change.	Episode 17 “Lake Laogai” Emphasises the moral tension between Zuko’s duty and conscience.	Episode 12 “The Western Air Temple” Focuses on Zuko’s apology to the Gaang and his struggle for acceptance.
Episode 20 “The Siege of the North, Part 2” Highlights Zuko’s isolation and growing uncertainty about his path.	Episode 20 “The Crossroads of Destiny” Marks a major setback where Zuko rejects growth and recommits to the Fire Nation.	Episode 13 “The Firebending Masters” Reframes the meaning of Firebending and his cultural identity.
		Episodes 18-21, “Sozin’s Comet” especially “Part 3: Into the Inferno” Completes Zuko’s arc as he confronts Azula and helps Aang defeat the Fire Lord.

Table 2: Zuko-focused episode selection for viewing. Green highlights indicate opportunities for deeper analysis.

6.2.1 Identity “Who am I ?”

Episode focus:

“The Storm”, specifically the Agni Kai; “Zuko Alone”

Key aims:

- Explore how Identity is shaped by family, culture, expectations, and power
- Practise vocabulary for self-description, emotions, and values

Possible activities:

- Guided viewing of screenshots/short clips and mark audiovisual elements such as colours, light, camera angles, music, body language, etc., using sticky notes or digital tags (Miro, OneNote...).
- Identity webs: students create simple identity mind maps (age, gender, class, language...) for themselves and Zuko, then discuss and mark which aspects feel chosen or imposed. This web gets updated with each viewing of an episode.
- Venn diagrams can be used to compare two characters or the same character during two different times in history to track similarities, differences, and changes.
- Scaffolded sentence starters: “Zuko sees himself as..., Others see him as..., He wants to be...)
- Short reflective writing about a situation where expectations from others conflicted with personal beliefs, optionally anonymised or fictionalised.

6.2.2 Diversity “Beyond Enemy Images”

Episode focus:

“Zuko Alone”, “The Crossroads of Destiny”

Key aims:

- Identify, question, and challenge stereotypes
- Practise multiperspectivity

Possible activities:

- Role cards (Earth Kingdom villagers, soldiers, Zuko, Katara...) to predict how and why they feel about someone and track their feelings about “the enemy”.
- Within their role, discussions using phrases such as “From my point of view..., I understand that... but...”
- Essentialising vs. nuanced phrases (all Earth Kingdom people are... vs. some Earth Kingdom people...) using Katara’s “it’s in your blood” line as a starting point. Students reformulate biased sentences into more precise, less stereotyping alternatives.
- “Missing Voices” Role-Playing task: students consider marginalised perspectives in the series and rewrite, act out, or draw those scenes.

6.2.3 Justice “Seeing Power Structures”

Episode focus:

Flashback to the throne room scenes in “The Storm” and “Zuko Alone”; coup scenes in “The Crossroads of Destiny”

Key aims:

- Build visual literacy around power and oppression
- Introduce basic vocabulary for and concepts of fairness and systemic injustice

Possible activities:

- Image freeze and description: students describe stills using spatial language (above, below, dark) and label emotions and the atmosphere (afraid, moody, angry, proud, light...).
- Symbol hunt: labelling symbols of power, fear, and resistance (flags, ...)
- “Power ladder”: students place characters on a ladder from most to least powerful. Discussions about what it means to have power.
- Age-appropriate historical and contemporary images (Japanese Imperialism, Trump administration, Nazi Germany) to compare with Fire Nation imagery, using simple comparative language “similar to..., different because...”

6.2.4 Action “Honour and Accountability”

Episode focus:

“The Western Air Temple”

Key aims:

- Practise language for apology, responsibility, accountability, and change
- Reflect on realistic forms of action in student contexts

Possible activities:

- Character journey storyboard or timeline that tracks small or big acts of change, as well as setbacks, to show the non-linear nature of transformation.
- “Hope Core”: audiovisual task where students collect scenes and quotes that show change and suggest hope.
- “What would you do?”: Fictional conflicts based on the series and in real life (bullying, exclusion, gossiping) are presented. Students identify small actions they could take when they see unfairness at school or in the *A:TLA* universe, using the structure “If..., I can...”
- Brainstorm features of a good apology based on Zuko’s apology. Students practise writing using key phrases “I’m sorry for..., It was wrong because..., Next time I will...”.

7. Limitations & Further Research

This study offered theoretical and practical contributions to the integration of anti-bias education and multimodal media analysis in the secondary EFL classroom. However, several limitations regarding methodology, corpus selection, framework construction, and pedagogical application must be acknowledged. Some of these have been discussed in earlier chapters. These limitations shape this study and its findings and offer directions for further research.

7.1 Methodological limitation

7.1.1 Qualitative Design and Interpretation

The study employs a qualitative, critical, multimodal analysis of a series grounded in theory and a synthesised analytical framework. As discussed in Chapter 3, this method prioritises interpretation over generalisability. While this approach is needed for analysing how meaning is constructed through audiovisual elements and narratives in media, it is inherently interpretative. It relies heavily on the single researcher's engagement with the material. The findings reflect one possible way of reading the text, which is shaped by the researcher's cultural lens, educational background, and personal experiences with the media. The iterative inductive-deductive process means that the framework itself evolved during analysis, indicating that the tool was not fixed from the get-go. As a result, the analyses of the episodes are not entirely uniform, although no major changes were made that would skew the outcomes. Future studies might incorporate collaborative work or student perspectives to show diverse interpretations.

7.1.2 Absence of empirical classroom data

Although the framework was designed for general classroom use, the activities are informed only by the researcher's own teaching experience. Thus, some classroom applications may have been designed with overly optimistic assumptions about what is possible in the classroom. Furthermore, the study does not include empirical testing in real classrooms. The effectiveness, accessibility, and practicality of the suggested activities and the framework as a whole remain unknown. A gap noted in Chapter 2

remains unsolved, as it is still unclear whether the framework supports the shift from recognition to ethical action. Acknowledging these influences is essential in critical research and underscores the need for future studies conducted by individuals from diverse backgrounds and pedagogical experiences.

7.2 Limitations of the synthesised anti-bias media analysis framework

The framework developed for this study integrated the Social Justice Standards, McLaughlin and DeVoogd's critical literacy (2004), Eder's clock of character (2010), Doelker's visual literacy (2015), and Doering's affective cognitive theory (2013). While this combination proved helpful for the analytical process, the frameworks are, as noted in Chapter 2, largely theoretical, and their practical applicability must be tested. Besides the SJS, which have been applied in practice, albeit other methods are preferred, the other frameworks lack empirical validation and classroom tools.

7.2.1 Overlap between IDJA Domains and their Demands

As the analysis revealed, Identity, Diversity, Justice, and Action are deeply interconnected. This aligns with the core of anti-bias education, as these domains don't just exist in a vacuum, but all influence each other. In practice, students might find it difficult to distinguish between and navigate these domains. Teachers might need to refine and reduce the categories depending on the aims and the language level of the class.

The framework also requires a certain level of analytical and cultural knowledge, as well as multimodal awareness, that may exceed what can reasonably be expected of secondary learners and teachers. In the classroom, extensive scaffolding will be needed to approach concepts such as symbolism, ideology, or moral agency. Teaching with the framework "as is" will overwhelm young learners, no matter their English proficiency.

7.2.2 Transferability to other media forms

Although multimodality is central to this study, the framework was only applied to one animated television series. Future research could test its adaptability not only with other series but also with graphic novels, short films, video games, commercials, YouTube videos, TikToks, or music videos. This would test the framework's transferability and reveal specific potential and challenges when applied across genres and media.

7.3 Corpus Limitation

7.3.1 Narrow corpus by design

The corpus was intentionally focused on four Zuko-focused episodes from *Avatar: The Last Airbender*. This narrow selection was made because it provides a coherent, manageable arc that mirrors the IDJA progression and allows for analysis within limited lesson time. However, this also limits the range of themes that can be discussed. Zuko's arc highlights themes of imperialism, nationalism, identity formation, moral agency, trauma, and belonging. Yet other forms of bias are not represented, such as racism, queerphobia, ableism, and misogyny. This corpus alone significantly limits which anti-bias concepts can be addressed.

7.3.2 Other characters and storylines

Other characters could offer entry points to explore different aspects of the IDJA domains, like examining how gendered expectations of leadership shape characters like Katara or Azula, how disability and empowerment are navigated through Toph's narrative, how misogyny is instilled in young boys through Sokka, or how the experiences of the Water Tribe and Air Nomads embody indigenous identity and genocide. Expanding the corpus to include a wider range of characters would therefore deepen the anti-bias themes available for analysis and allow for a more comprehensive understanding of the series' engagement with social justice.

Additionally, each analytical focus, such as leitmotif, trauma representation, or imperial architecture, could have been a standalone study. By covering many domains simultaneously, this study treats most aspects at a surface level.

7.3.3 *A:TLA* as an imperfect Text

Avatar: The Last Airbender itself is not a flawless text, nor should it have to be, but one should be aware of the criticisms. While it is widely praised for its representation and cultural hybridity, some scholars and viewers argue that the show's blending of Asian and Indigenous cultures verges on being disrespectful and cultural appropriation, raising questions about the adaptation of real traditions within fictional worlds (Wang 2022).

Moreover, even progressive narratives can unconsciously perpetuate ideologies. As Kerr (2024, 1026) notes, *A:TLA* reflects Michael Billig's (1995) concept of "banal nationalism", which normalises the division of the world into nations as a natural order, despite the show's critique of extreme nationalism. These tensions highlight that *A:TLA*, like all media, carries biases, which further limit the scope of the anti-bias themes accessible through this corpus.

7.4 Anti-Bias education in Swiss EFL contexts

Although the study aligns with the values of the Lehrplan 21, Swiss secondary classrooms vary in linguistic diversity, student motivation, school environment, teacher experience and autonomy, and time constraints, among other factors. *A:TLA* also deals with sensitive topics, which, with students' own experiences, will shape their response that demands teacher expertise that cannot be assumed by everyone. These contextual factors may influence how easily the framework can be adapted. For future research, empirical studies focusing on Swiss secondary classrooms could investigate how teachers implement anti-bias principles, students' readiness to discuss sensitive and complex topics in English, institutional support or constraints, and the assessment possibilities of anti-bias competences. Such studies would ground the theoretical contributions of this thesis in empirical educational practice.

7.5 Summary

This study's limitations reflect the complexities of implementing anti-bias education and multimodal analysis into EFL contexts. While the synthesised framework provides a conceptual tool, its practical use, broader applicability, and effectiveness need to be tested. Nevertheless, this study's limitations highlight the potential for future research that bridges anti-bias education, media literacy, and meaningful classroom activities.

8. Conclusion

This thesis was set out to explore how anti-bias education can be meaningfully integrated into the secondary EFL classroom through the analysis using *Avatar: The Last Airbender* as an example. The study argues that media and fiction can function as a powerful pedagogical tool for developing anti-bias competences, critical media literacy, empathy, and social awareness among teenage learners.

To address these aims, this thesis synthesised established frameworks from anti-bias education, critical literacy, visual literacy, character analysis, and affective-cognitive media theory into a coherent Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework. This framework was then applied to four episodes centred around the character Zuko, whose arc reflects the anti-bias progression through Identity, Diversity, Justice, and Action. Through a qualitative, critical, multimodal analysis, the study illustrated how meaning is constructed in *A:TLA* through symbolism, character constellation, world-building, and audiovisual cues. The analysis showed that Zuko's journey can be read visually and textually as a narrative of identity formation, cross-cultural empathy, systemic injustice, and moral agency, all core themes of anti-bias education.

8.1 Research Questions

In response to RQ1 the study showed that existing anti-bias frameworks (SJS, Derman-Sparks) can be adapted for media analysis when complemented with other frameworks and tools that decode visual storytelling and symbolism. The synthesised framework supports students in analysing what is represented, how it is represented, and why it is meaningful. This addresses the gaps identified in the introduction, specifically the lack of concrete models and activities that integrate anti-bias education with media literacy and support learners in moving beyond recognition toward deeper engagement and ethical action.

In response to RQ2, the analysis of Zuko's arc demonstrated how character representation in *A:TLA* can be a model for the four domains of anti-bias education. Zuko's shift in how he sees himself, his encounters across cultural boundaries, his complicity in systemic injustice, and his eventual resistance to authoritarian ideology provide

accessible entry points for discussions about privilege, prejudice, accountability, and transformation. The multimodal elements of the series, like colours, lighting, leitmotifs, camera angles, gestures, symbolism, characters, and plot points, provide layers through which students can develop critical analysis skills. These findings show how character representation in media can be meaningfully integrated into the EFL anti-bias education.

In response to RQ3 the study shows that the adapted framework is not limited to *A:TLA*. While the series' complex world-building and thematic depth make it, in particular, a strong example, the frameworks' multimodal and critical approach allows it to be transferred to other media. It encourages students to move from perception to interpretation, reflection, and action, which is a structure that supports classroom routines and strengthens analytical skills. In Chapter 6, general guidelines were illustrated that support the transferability of the framework to other media. These insights were translated into classroom practices for *A:TLA* through guided analysis of pressure point scenes and scaffolded tasks. Although the teaching ideas are empirically untested, they illustrate potential for anti-bias education in the Swiss secondary curriculum.

8.2 Final Reflection

Overall, this thesis argues that when anti-bias education and media literacy are combined, they support learners in understanding themselves and others, questioning dominant narratives, recognising structural injustice, and imagining possibilities for ethical action. Fictional media like *A:TLA* offer a space to explore and develop these competences. In the EFL classroom, where language learning, cultural learning, and identity exploration intersect, these approaches can foster critical thinking and empathy. This study calls for a continued exploration of children's media as a resource for anti-bias learning.

Beyond its academic contributions, this study also represents the merging of my interests in pop culture media and inclusive teaching. The research process allowed me to explore how these areas intersect and how complex social issues can be discussed in an accessible way. I gained valuable insights for my future teaching, and I look forward to implementing and further refining these ideas in a real classroom.

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10. Appendices

Appendix A Season 1, Episode 12 «The Storm»

Table 3: Observational Notes with Timestamps for Season 1, Episode 12 "The Storm"

Timestamp	Notes
3.00 – 3.48	<p>Zuko's theme soundtrack is very imposing, gives off very bad vibes. The loud horns announce troubles. Stark contrast to theme soundtrack of the Avatar which are light strings.</p> <p>Iroh and Zuko fight about which direction to take the ship because of bad weather. Zuko announces that the safety of the crew doesn't matter. Finding the Avatar is more important than any individual's safety. Iroh defends him by saying that he doesn't mean it and is just all worked up. Iroh is way too forgiving. Zuko did just say something incredibly mean. We see hot headedness of Zuko and the forgiving and good nature of Iroh.</p> <p>Iroh was right about the storm, and the crew is blaming Zuko for not going the other way. Iroh tries to soften the blow by saying that it was a lucky guess – It was not, Iroh is incredibly smart and knew what he was doing.</p>
5.01 – 5.57	<p>Zuko goes up to the lieutenant and says that he "better learn some respect", or he will teach it to him. Lieutenant answers with: "what do you know about respect?" Iroh makes a worried panicked face in the background and face-palms his face. The lieutenant says that Zuko doesn't care about anyone but himself. "What can you expect from a spoiled prince?" -> Zoom in on Zuko's eyebrows and he immediately readies himself to fight the lieutenant. Strong intense soundtrack.</p> <p>Iroh breaks up the fight saying they're all tired and need a bowl of soup. Zuko's is mad because "he doesn't need help to keep order on the ship.</p>
9.53 -	<p>The ship crew is angry with Zuko's behaviour. Uncle Iroh steps in to tell the story of how and why Zuko went through so much and tries to reason with the crew.</p>
10.20 – 11.45	<p>Flashback: Colour change, Different theme – sadder? Zuko tries to enter the war chamber, but the guards won't let him. Iroh again tries to cheer him up by saying that these meetings are boring. Zuko's asks "If I'm going to rule this nation one day, don't you think I need to start learning as much as I can?" Zuko looks so different unrecognisable. So much younger, full of hope. No shaved head, full open eyes, full eyebrows and most importantly no scar. Iroh lets him in under the condition that he doesn't speak, as these old folks are sensitive.</p>

	The war room looks so imposing. Large pillars, large table, the people at the table look so small. The Fire Lord is far away from the people surrounded by fire and elevated. You can barely see him. The Fire Lord's costume is pointy, military fashion and yet regal.
13.27- 14.23	One of the war plans is to sacrifice an entire division as a decoy against the Earth Kingdom. Zuko is enraged "You can't sacrifice an entire division like that. These soldiers love and defend our nation. How can you betray them?" Shriill sound to show how bad and shocking his action was.
17.06 – 18.45	Fire Lord became angry with the prince, the flames surrounding him become bigger. The only way Zuko could redeem himself was through an Agni Kai, a fire duel. Zuko thought he was going to duel the lord he disrespected but he had to duel the fire lord, his father. He looks so scared, he was just a child.
19.16 -19.49	Zuko begged for mercy from his father saying he only had the fire nation's best interest at heart. The fire lord is a faceless figure. Only seen from the back or through shadow. He has a strong intimidating aura, and deep voice. "You will fight for your honour." Zuko doesn't want to fight him. Fire Lord says he will learn respect and suffering will be his teacher. Zuko is on his knees crying. Uncle Iroh looked away while Azula, Zuko's sister, and general Zhao were watching with delight, as Zuko is screaming in the background as his face is getting scorched by the Fire Lord. By not fighting Zuko has shown great "weakness" and as punishment he was banished was sent to capture the Avatar. Only then he could return with his honour. The Avatar gives Zuko hope and Purpose. This is reflected by the back-and-forth shots of Zuko's "perfect" idyllic childhood and him in the ship basement. Overlaying shots of young hopeful Zuko and angry scarred Zuko. The Ship gets struck by lightning.
20.12 – 20.30	The tower was hit and one of the helmsmen was stuck on the tower. Zuko went up there in the pouring rain and unstable condition of the tower to help him. Iroh redirects the lightning. Zuko looks proud of himself.
21.45-	The Avatar flies over the ship and Zuko is dealt with the choice of going after him or getting the crew to safety. He chooses to get the crew to safety. Zuko apologizes to Iroh which he accepts. Aang and the gang head out of the water right in front the ship where Zuko and Aang have eye contact. Maybe it was a confusion on both ends because neither acted the way they usually did. Zuko seemed to hesitate for a bit.

Table 4: Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework applied to Season 1, Episode 12 "The Storm"

Framework Category	Prompts/ Key Observations
Visual Scene De-coder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="555 300 906 331">- Spontaneous meaning <li data-bbox="507 344 1390 618">Zuko's scenes feel tense and uncomfortable. His anger, the crew's understandable frustration and the flashbacks create a mix of dread and sympathy for the first time while watching the show. This is where you feel bad for Zuko, I pity him. I understand that Zuko is deeply conflicted and misunderstood but I also cannot his treatment of other especially the Avatar. <li data-bbox="555 685 810 716">- Literal meaning <li data-bbox="507 730 1390 1102">Zuko's ship is caught in a storm, which could have been avoided if Zuko had decided to being his crew to safety and not chase the Avatar. Uncle Iroh tells in a flashback how Zuko got his scar. Zuko spoke against the war plans of the Fire Lord, his father, which embarrassed him. In an Agni Kai, a fire duel, Zuko had to prove himself. Zuko didn't want to fight his father which ended up with him getting scarred on his face by his father. Zuko rescues a crew member, then faces another choice between chasing Aang or saving his crew. He chose to save his crew. <li data-bbox="555 1169 683 1200">- Mood <li data-bbox="507 1214 1390 1384">The storm itself mirrors inner turmoil: chaos, danger, fear and eventual calmness. For Zuko, the visuals emphasise isolation and surprised pain. The flashback is darker, muted in tone, emphasizing trauma and loss of innocence.
Identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="555 1411 1050 1442">- Personal, cultural, social identity <li data-bbox="507 1456 1390 1536">Zuko: male, Fire Nation prince (upper class, royalty), but scarred and exiled (outsider within his own culture). <li data-bbox="507 1550 1342 1581">Iroh: older male, general, embodies wisdom, patience, forgiveness. <li data-bbox="555 1648 906 1680">- Audiovisual elements <li data-bbox="507 1693 1390 1863">Zuko's scar and shaved head are constant reminder of exile and punishment. He has an extremely imposing soundtrack with horns and drums, dark framing. Which contrast the brighter and softer framing of Aang and Iroh's calm tone and light humour. <li data-bbox="507 1886 1390 2011">In the flashback scenes Zuko's seems almost unrecognisable. He has a boyish charm wide eyes full of curiosity. A stark difference from his intimidating demeanour now.

	<p>- Language</p> <p>His language is harsh, demanding respect, but his voice is juvenile showing his fractured identity. He is commanding, aggressive and blunt “You better learn respect”. In the flashback he sounds naïve and soft, showing that he was just a kid.</p> <p>- Representation</p> <p>Zuko represent the struggle for honour, need for recognition. But he is the aggressor, chasing after the Avatar. He is the prince of an imperialist nation and holds the values of an imperialist nation. Commander of ship but also just a teenager. He represents anger and unresolved trauma. He is angry and yet so deeply sad.</p> <p>- Self-perception</p> <p>The words of his father shape who he is today, for worse. And how other people react to his scar, which just further proves to him that he is not a good person. The only person who doesn’t see him this way is Iroh. Showing him that he is just a teen after all.</p> <p>- Stereotypes</p> <p>Up until this episode he was the stereotypical villain. He is pure evil chasing after the Avatar with no regards for anyone but himself.</p> <p>- Contradiction/Conflicts</p> <p>Zuko sees himself as dishonoured and despised, yet his actions, saving a crew member, prove he does care. His inner conflict between compassion and rage is clear.</p> <p>- Identification</p> <p>Viewers will empathize with Zuko despite his problems, his trauma humanized him. Many can relate to not feeling like enough, especially at young age there is so much pressure and fear of disappointing one’s parents.</p>
Diversity	<p>- How are relationships across different social groups (e.g., nations, cultures, abilities, ages) portrayed? Are individuals showed beyond group labels? What might be missing?</p> <p>Zuko vs. his crew → tension between royalty and common soldiers. Iroh mediates between them, bridging hierarchy.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the character show pride in their identity and respect others? - How do characters navigate between different social, cultural, or community spaces? <p>Zuko's royal upbringing isolates him from his crew. Iroh respects differences and uses wisdom to soften conflicts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are differences shown as enriching, problematic, or threatening? <p>How does the visual design signal inclusion, exclusion, or hierarchy? Fire Lord elevated on a throne, surrounded by fire. Zuko kneeling in submission during the Agni Kai. Ship layout: Zuko commands from above deck, crew obey below.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What would change if the story was told from another character's point of view or different setting (period, culture)? <p>From the lieutenant's view, Zuko is a spoiled, reckless prince. From Zuko's view, he is broken, desperate for honour.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Were there moments that challenged your thinking or made you uncomfortable? <p>The Agni Kai scene is disturbing — a child scarred permanently by his own father. It forces reflection on abuse, power, and authoritarian parenting.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do you compare your own background and experiences (ethnicity, gender, sexuality, class, age, religion etc.) with those of the characters?
Justice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What forms of bias or injustices (e.g., discrimination, war, imperialism, inequality) are present? What are the consequences? <p>Fire Nation = imperialistic, authoritarian. Is the reason why the 4 nations are at war.</p> <p>Fire Lord Ozai = absolute ruler, abuses power, greed. Abuses his son. The reason why Zuko has the scar and why the world is still at war.</p> <p>Prince Zuko: victim of unjust power yet wields power over his crew. Discriminates against other nations. Benefits from being the exiled prince.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which characters benefit from/ has power? How do they use or lose it? Zuko was once in great power he was the prince of an imperialist nation. Fire Nation sacrifices soldiers as pawns. Zuko is punished for compassion, for speaking up for soldiers. - Who gets away with what and who suffers? Fire Lord benefits from cruelty, nobody can say anything to him. Crew suffers from Zuk's recklessness. Zuko suffers and befits dorm systematic authoritarianism and his father's abuse. - Whose perspective dominates the story? Whose voices are missing or marginalized? The voices of the normal folk are missing. - How are systems of oppression visually encoded (e.g., language, architecture, uniforms, lighting, space)? Ozai as faceless, towering figure. Throne room is cold (even though surrounded by fire), elevated and intimidating. On the ship there is rigid hierarchy, Zuko at top but still powerless. The Fire nations uniforms are black and red, pointed sharp edges, a lot of metal. - Do characters symbolize broader social conflicts or ideologies? What real-world social or political issues are mirrored in the show (e.g., racism, imperialism, classism)? Fire nation imperialism parallels real-world colonialism, authoritarian regimes. The creators said it was based on Japan (I think). Zuko's scar is a mark of trauma and social stigma. Being "ugly" and standards of beauty and the privileged it can bring with it. - What emotional reactions did these injustices evoke in you? Sympathy, anger at injustice, and unease. Especially towards parental abuse and the silencing of compassion.
Action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do characters resist injustice or act for change? What skills, values, or mindsets (empathy, responsibility, agency) help them? Zuko speaks up for soldiers that were going to be used as pawns in battle. He embarrasses the Fire Lord showing his weakness, which gets

	<p>him punished. Later he risks himself to save a crew member, a small redemption.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the risks and consequences of speaking out? Zuko lost everything for speaking against his father. He got scarred and is exiled. The crew risks punishment for confronting Zuko. - What language or actions express fairness, protest, or resistance? “You can’t sacrifice an entire division like that. These soldiers love and defend our nation. How can you betray them?” - Are there examples of collective action or allyship? What strategies are used, and how effective are they? Crew stands united in blaming Zuko. Iroh protects Zuko by telling his story, softening crew resentment. - What narrative or visual tools suggest change or hope (e.g., inspirational scenes, colour shifts, music)? Storm clearing = resolution. Zuko apologizes to Iroh = growth. The flashback scenes of his perfect childhood scenes that the Zuko is holding onto hope. And that young boy still out there somewhere. The parallel between Zuko and Aang’s arcs show hope in flawed characters. - How might your interpretation inspire action or reflection? What should viewers take away from this story? Trauma shapes people but compassion can guide choices. Authority and honour should be questioned, not blindly obeyed. People are more complex than hero vs. villain. - What were the creator intention? How does that affect interpretation? Likely to deepen character complexity, showing that even villains have pain and humanity. This challenges stereotypes of good vs. evil and build empathy.
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Appendix B Season 2, Episode 7 “Zuko Alone”

Table 5: Observational Notes with Timestamps for Season 2, Episode 7 "Zuko Alone"

Timestamp	Notes
01.55	Zuko's is tracking alone on his ostrich horse through the remote earth kingdom villages, he looks dishevelled, tired and hungry. He has short hair, common looking earth kingdom clothes and straw hat to disguise his face. He smells food and was ready to fight for that food by reaching for his sword but then he sees that that food his for a man and his pregnant wife and lets them be. He leaves them alone. He is exhausted, starts drifting in and out of consciousness and starts dreaming about his mother.
3.00	He enters a village for food but doesn't have enough money. He meets Earth Kingdom soldiers who are supposed to protect the village from the Fire Nation but are "thugs" instead. Zuko meets a boy who takes him to his house to feed. The village looks barren, and hot. Sounds reflect that. Zuko has no fight in him.
4.37	The nice family takes him in. The boy bothers Zuko with personal questions for which he answers with curt answers. Dad doesn't want the son to bother him "the man's past is his business.". Zuko hammers on his thumb when the boy asks how he got his scar. Funny comedic effect because Zuko is caught off guard when he is so brooding all the time.
6.20	Flashback: Dreamy, milky sequence. Red dominates. The fire Nation palace is grand, royal, walled up, guarded from the outside world. Fire Nation Palace Zuko and his mother are feeding turtle ducks. They have fun, she is loving. They get a letter from general Iroh from the front lines where he talks about burning the city Ba Sing Se to the ground. They all laugh. Showing how normal war talk is and that they're conditioned from a young age to think that the Fire Nation is superior. He gets a dagger as a gift from Iroh which belonged to the general from the Earth Kingdom. Zuko and his mother stand up against Azula when she insults Iroh saying he wouldn't be a good Fire Lord.
9.34	Zuko sleeps in a barn. The boy steals Zuko's swords. Zuko doesn't get angry but instead shows him how to use them. He is smiling and isn't wearing his hat. The boy compares Zuko to his older brother who also used to show him things like this. Touching moment.
10.44	The mother gives Zuko a meal package to get him though for the next few days. When the soldiers from earlier come to tell them the son's battalion got caught by the Fire Nation. They remind the family of what the Fire Nation does to their prisoners: Dress them in fire nation clothing send

	them to the front lines without armour. Zuko steps in to non-verbally tell them off.
11.47	Flashback: Zuko's mother tearfully tells her children that Iroh's son didn't make the war.
12.05	Zuko is reminded of that when he hears that the brother of the boy is dead, he feels bad, he lowers his face, maybe also in ashamed. He gives the boy his dagger he got as a child. "Never give up without a fight". Co-medic moment where the boy first reads the inscription "made in earth kingdom"
12.43	Flashback: Azula belittles his knife skills. Iroh comes back home. Zuko thinks it's because they won the war but it's because Iroh is sad that his only child is dead. Zuko is also sad. The family holds an audience with the Fire Lord Azulon where they have to answer questions about him. Zuko struggles while Azula aces the questions. Zuko's father's whole face is still not shown, building greater mystery as to who this great villain is. Zuko shows his skills but fails in comparison to Azula. His mother consoles him "No I loved watching you. That's who you are, Zuko, someone who keeps fighting even though it's hard". Ozai suggests he becomes the new fire lord instead of Iroh. The fire lord gets fury that he would suggest something like this. Azula tells Zuko that the Fire Lord was so angry that he has to sacrifice his first-born son to understand that the Fire Lord would never betray his first-born son like this. To calm him down Zuko tells himself that "Azula always lies" like a mantra.
17.16	The mom goes to Zuko for help. The boy got in trouble with the thugs and pulled a knife on them, they took him away. Zuko said he will go help, probably also because he feels guilty for having given him the knife.
17.48	Zuko confronts the soldiers "You're not soldiers, you are bullies, you are freeloaders, abusing your power, mostly over women and kids (..) You are sick cowards messing with a family, who's already lost one son to the war". They fight with Zuko using his fire bending powers only his swords. Zuko hits his head.
20.08	Flashback: Zuko's mother wakes him up from sleep. "Everything I've done, is one to protect you (...) No matter how things may seem to change, never forget who you are." She then disappears into the night.
20.34	Full of anger Zuko stands up using his fire powers, revealing himself. You can hear Zuko's/ fire nations light motif, showing that his "evil" side has returned. When the soldiers ask him who he is he answers that he is prince Zuko, the son to Ursa and the Fire Lord, and is the heir to fire

	nation. When he wants to give back the dagger to the boy, the mom protects him. The boy says that he hates Zuko.
21.44	Flashback: Zuko wakes up looking for his mom. She is gone and the Fire Lord has died. Coronation of Ozai to the Fire Lord. The Royal family is wearing all white and gold. The others are in red hoods. "All Hails to Fire Lord Ozai" – resembles a lot of the imagery used by Nazi Germany. Fire as decoration. Ozai looking over everything the soldiers and the people look so small. Red, black, grim, so imposing, fear. Zuko looks so scared.
23.27	Zuko is yet again exiled from a place. He walks out into the sunset as the village people are watching.

Table 6: Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework applied to Season 2, Episode 7 "Zuko Alone"

<p>Visual Scene Decoder</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is your immediate gut reaction to the scene? The episode feels heavy, sorrowful, and deeply personal. My first reaction is sympathy for Zuko, who is displaced, exhausted, and on the edge of collapse. His interactions with the villagers create a sense of tragic irony. He comes from the Fire Nation yet is hiding with its victims. - What is literally depicted? See above, but in short: Zuko in disguise travels through Earth Kingdom villages, encounters poverty, cruelty, and a kind family, and recalls childhood memories of his mother. Scenes move between the barren Earth Kingdom and warm-toned but oppressive Fire Nation flashbacks. - What mood or atmosphere is communicated? Barren, hostile landscapes → isolation and estrangement. Flashbacks drenched in red and gold → a childhood surrounded by wealth, power, and militarism but also violence and fear. Barn, family meals, comedic moments → fleeting warmth that contrasts with Zuko's inner turmoil. Final coronation of Ozai → spectacle of hierarchy and fascist overtones. Together, these visuals communicate loneliness, guilt, and Zuko's fragile search for identity. The use of framing (Ozai's face hidden, palace walls looming) heightens mystery and power imbalance.
<p>Identity How are identities constructed and represented?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do we learn about the character's personal, cultural, and social identity (race, gender, class, language, etc.)? do these interact or conflict?

	<p>Zuko once royal clad in expensive armour accompanied by the military, is now stripped of his privileges. He hides in peasant clothes and avoids firebending, surprising his cultural identity. His scar marks him visibly as “other”/scary, and he hides it with a hat. His cultural upbringing (imperial superiority, war normalized) conflicts with his developing empathy for ordinary people.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are these identities made visible or invisible through audiovisual choices (e.g., costume, voice, framing)? <p>Costume: earth-tone rags disguise his status. Combine by an ostrich horse.</p> <p>Voice: curt, reserved answers, he avoids emotional expression.</p> <p>Leitmotif: Zuko’s usual motif noticeably absent until he at the end when he gets angry starts firebending. Otherwise very subdued, light.</p> <p>Flashback: palace grandeur emphasises class privilege and indoctrination</p> <p>The creators draw on colour symbolism (red = Fire Nation, violence; earthy browns = simplicity, poverty).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What language contribute to identity (choice of words, formality, accent, self-expression) <p>His dialogue is clipped, defensive (“It’s none of your business”), yet moments of warmth slip through when teaching the boy swords or recalling his mother.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What does the character represent (values, struggles, ideologies, socially, politically, emotionally)? <p>Zuko embodies the struggle between inherited ideology (imperialism, honour culture) and emerging empathy/justice. He symbolizes inner conflict: villain vs. hero, prince vs. exile.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who or what influences their self-perception? <p>His mother instilled love and moral courage (“never forget who you are”), while his father and sister belittled and manipulated him. This dual influence shapes his fractured self.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the character challenge or reinforce stereotypes? <p>He begins as the “banished prince/villain” trope but this episode complicates him, he shows kindness, humour, and self-doubt.</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does the character view themselves and how do others perceive them? Are there contradictions ? How are internal conflicts depicted? <p>He sees himself as dishonoured, unworthy. Others see him as a suspicious stranger, or a brave hero. Contradictions are central to his arc. The boy in this episode who befriend Zuko sees him as an older brother. And the first person Zuko has encountered in years that didn't judge him until the end when he found out that he is a fire bender.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - With whom do viewers identify, and why? <p>Viewers empathize with Zuko's suffering and longing for acceptance. His humanity shines through his vulnerability and small moments of kindness.</p>
<p>Diversity How are differences portrayed and what interactions do they create?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are relationships across different social groups (e.g., nations, cultures, abilities, ages) portrayed? Are individuals showed beyond group labels? What might be missing? <p>The episode contrasts Fire Nation royalty and Earth Kingdom peasants. Despite cast cultural differences, Zuko bonds with the family showing common humanity and domesticity like sharing food, laughter, teaching swords. The villagers are more than just victims, they are parents, siblings, individuals with dreams and pain. And being not- Fire nation doesn't make anyone a good person either, like the Earth Kingdom soldiers that act superior to other villagers. Zuko is more than a "Fire Nation prince" he is a lonely boy longing for love.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the character show pride in their identity and respect others? <p>The family is incredibly proud of their oldest son being in war and fighting. They are very respectful. On the other hand, the soldiers are also very prideful in their titles but show very little respect to others. Zuko used to be very prideful of who is and where he came from but now as a banished prince seeing the horrors of the Fire Nation, he is less proud.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do characters navigate between different social, cultural, or community spaces? <p>Zuko moves between disguising himself as Earth Kingdom peasant and recalling his Fire Nation past. He never fully belongs to either. He changes his appearance, hides his abilities.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are differences shown as enriching, problematic, or threatening? Enriching: moments of connection with the boy/family. He feels normal for a while. He isn't being judged. Problematic/threatening: his Fire Nation identity makes him dangerous to them. - How does the visual design signal inclusion, exclusion, or hierarchy? Earth Kingdom (villages) -> barren, struggling under war Fire Nation (Royal Palace) -> ornate, militaristic, fascist spectacle. Hierarchy is coded in costume, architecture, and lighting. - What would change if the story was told from another character's point of view or different setting (period, culture)? If told from the boy's perspective, Zuko's might first appear as cool mysterious older brother type that then betrays him and seems untrustworthy and dangerous. It would also deal more about the horrors of war and losing one's brother, living in struggle and despite that always choosing to be kind. - Were there moments that challenged your thinking or made you uncomfortable? Child soldiers sent to the front lines without armour. The earth kingdom soldiers taking advantage of other people. How the royal family was so happy about the takedown of Ba Sing Se and how comfortable they are with war. Azula's and Ozai's cruelty framed as playful. Zuko's mother leaving him alone. The villager's hatred of Zuko after learning who is, based on the fact that he is a fire bender and not having done anything bad. - How do you compare your own background and experiences (ethnicity, gender, sexuality, class, age, religion etc.) with those of the characters? Viewers may compare their own family dynamics, feelings of exclusion, or experiences of prejudice with Zuko's, creating empathy through shared struggles. Viewers might have experienced war themselves or be judged for who they are.
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<p>Justice</p> <p>What power structures are shown and how are they challenged?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What forms of bias or injustices (e.g., discrimination, war, imperialism, inequality) are present? What are the consequences? Fire Nation imperialism, war crimes, forced conscription, dehumanization. Class inequality, peasants starving while royalty feasts. Child soldiers, systemic cruelty. - Which characters benefit from/ has power? How do they use or lose it? Fire Nation royalty holds ultimate power (Ozai, Azulon). Local “soldiers” abuse power to oppress the weak. Zuko resists both systems, but at great cost. - Who gets away with what and who suffers? Royals (Azula, Ozai) benefit from war. Ordinary Earth Kingdom families suffer loss and oppression. Zuko, caught in between, suffers both as victim and complicit member of the system. - Whose perspective dominates the story? Whose voices are missing or marginalized? Zuko’s, this is his subjective, fragmented memory. The villagers’ perspectives are underrepresented but hinted at. - How are systems of oppression visually encoded (e.g., language, architecture, uniforms, lighting, space)? Fire Nation palace walls = isolation and superiority. Red uniforms = militarism. Coronation = fascist spectacle of power. - Do characters symbolize broader social conflicts or ideologies? Zuko symbolizes imperialism’s human cost. The family represents those crushed under empire. Azula embodies ruthless ideology. - What real-world social or political issues are mirrored in the show (e.g., racism, imperialism, classism)? Imperialism/colonialism. Fascist aesthetics (Fire Lord’s coronation). Child soldiers/propaganda. Isolated remote villagers are left behind - What emotional reactions did these injustices evoke in you?
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	Sadness at Ursa's disappearance, anger at the soldiers' cruelty, pity for Zuko's loneliness.
<p>Action</p> <p>What responses to injustice are modelled and what might we do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do characters resist injustice or take action for change? What skills, values, or mindsets (empathy, responsibility, agency) help them? Zuko resists the abusive "soldiers" and defends the boy's family. He also resists internalized propaganda by feeling guilt and empathy. Empathy, responsibility, martial skill, perseverance. - What are the risks and consequences of speaking out? Zuko revealing himself as Fire Nation prince, he loses the villagers' trust and is rejected again. Speaking out isolates him. - What language or actions express fairness, protest, or resistance? Zuko confronts bullies: "You're not soldiers, you are cowards." His words expose corruption. - Are there examples of collective action or allyship? What strategies are used, and how effective are they? Limited, the family cannot resist, so Zuko acts alone. But the story hints at the need for collective resistance against empire. - What narrative or visual tools suggest change or hope (e.g., inspirational scenes, colour shifts, music)? Flashbacks of Ursa = hope rooted in love. Small moments of humour/light (hammering thumb, sword teaching). Music shifts when Zuko accepts his identity. - How might your interpretation inspire action or reflection? War dehumanizes both oppressors and victims. Personal identity is shaped by struggle and choice, not birth. - What were the creator intention? How does that affect interpretation? To humanize Zuko, deepen his backstory, and show the moral costs of empire. It positions him for transformation from antagonist to ally.

Appendix C Season 2, Episode 20 “The Crossroads of Destiny”

Table 7: Observational Notes with Timestamps for Season 2, Episode 20 “The Crossroads of Destiny”

Timestamp	Notes
2.47 – 3.07	Zuko and Iroh got invited to the King’s palace to serve tea. Zuko’s hair has grown quite a bit. The light motif is more hopeful light, complete switch up. They both look more content and relaxed. They thought they’d be here as conquerors. *Destiny is a funny thing”.
3.28 – 5.02	It’s actually a trick from Azula. Azula has taken control of the Dai Li special force of earth benders but with killer instinct. Iroh and Zuko fight together against the Dai Li. Zuko has a smirk on his face when Iroh insinuates that they will start fighting. Zuko is tired of running away and wants to face Azula. Th Dai Li get hold of quickly. He gets imprisoned.
5.40- 5.56	Zuko gets thrown in the cave with special crystals, where Katara also is at. She is first surprised but then is very quickly angry. Zuko is on his knees when they meet.
6.28 – 7.39	Iroh asks Aang, Sokka and Toph to help him get Zuko out. They are wary of him but they trust Toph’s instinct. Iroh also vouches for Zuko by saying that *there is still good inside him.” And Sokka says the good inside isn’t enough needs to be outside as well.
8.03 – 8.52	Katara is suspicious why Zuko is also the cell with her, she thinks it’s a trap so when Aang comes to save her he can capture him. Katara tells Zuko that he is terrible person for trying to capture the world’s last hope fore peace. She says that “being vile is in his blood”. Zuko defends himself by saying that he doesn’t know what he is talking about. He is being pretty calm in contrast to Katara’s anger. Katara cries that the fire Nation took away her mother. Zuko’s face softens up immediately. He apologies “I’m sorry, that’s something we have in common”. They found common ground. Katara realises that Zuko might not be that different from each other at all.
13.12 – 14.22, 16.10	Katara apologises for yelling. They have talk about how they’ve seen each other as enemies. Zuko wants to be freed of what his scar stands for and choose his destiny. Katara wants to use her water from the spirit oasis from the north pole to heal Zuko’s scar. Katara touches it, sharing a moment of intimacy. Aang and Iroh make it to the cave. Both hug their respective beloveds. Zuko and Aang look at each other suspiciously. Zuko feels betrayed that Iroh came there with Aang. Aang and Katara leave to save their friends. Katara and Zuko share a longing look. Motif really helps with that. Iroh explains how Zuko has gotten stronger and wiser and that now is the moment to his destiny (meaning not to chase

	<p>after the Avatar). Azula barges in and accuses both Zuko and Iroh of being traitors, but that there is still hope for Zuko. She manipulates him by saying that she has been plotting for this a long time and the only way they can win is together. He will have his honour back and his father's love. Iroh begs him to look into his heart and see what he truly wants. Zuko is left with an important choice. Amplified by shots of his profile without scar (good) and with scar (evil).</p>
16.46 -17.08	<p>Azula is fighting Aang and Katara. Zuko comes into the fight first seemingly attacking. But after intense eye contact with Aang Zuko decides to go after him instead of Azula. Zuo is consumed fight with anger and is fighting without thinking. Azula is pleased.</p>
17.21 – 19.16	<p>Aang and Zuko are fighting intensively. Zuko is attacking while Zuko is deflecting. Zukko's flames are big but on the verge of uncontrollable. Huge improvement in his skills. Zuko helps Azula when she was almost taken out by Katara. Now Zuko is fighting Katara "I thought you had changed" said Katara. Zuko answers "I have changed" while attacking her. Meaning that he has gotten stronger in skills and is not as "weak" anymore.</p>
19.39 – 22.19	<p>Katara is defeated by Zuko and Azula working together. The shot of Azula and Zuko together shows how powerful they could be. The Dai Li come to Azula's defence, and Aang realises that he can't defeat them all. Aang goes into Avatar state which intimidates Zuko. But Azula hits him with lightning. When Zuko and Azula get closer to conscienceless Aang in Katara's arms Iroh steps in giving them time to flee. Iroh is a very strong bender. When he sees that they have fled the scene he immediately stops fighting and lets himself be captured. This sight makes Zuko feel sad. But Iroh is definitely disappointed in Zuko. Which should make Zuko feel horrible as the only person who has always believed in him is now also disappointed in him.</p>
22.56 – 23.25	<p>The Fire Nation has captured Ba Sing Se. Zuko is guilt ridden "I betrayed uncle" Azula answers "No, He betrayed you. When you return home father will welcome you as a war hero." But Zuko doesn't think so because he still doesn't have the Avatar, that that won't restore his honour. Azula says that even without the Avatar he has restored his honour. Conflicting emotions in Zuko's face: proud, anger, guilt.</p>

Table 8: Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework applied to Season 2, Episode 20 "The Crossroads of Destiny"

<p>Visual Scene Decoder</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is your immediate gut reaction to the scene? The scenes feel tense and conflicted. There is both intimacies, Zuko and Katara in the crystal cave, and betrayal, Zuko sliding with Azula. My gut reaction is both hope (Zuko may finally change) and frustration (he falls back into old patterns). - What is literally depicted? See above. Zuko and Iroh are running a popular tea shop in Ba Sing Se, the capital city of the Earth Kingdom. They lured into the palace by Azula. Azula plans a coup with the Dai Li, for that she imprisons Katara, and the others. When Iroh and Zuko run away from the Dai Li, Zuko decides it's time to face Azula. He gets imprisonment as well with Katara in the crystal cave. Katara and Zuko have an emotional exchange where it may seem like Zuko might let go of chasing the Avatar but in the end, he decided to side with Azula. - What mood or atmosphere is communicated? The tea shop scenes are warm and domestic. The cave scenes are dim but intimate, and the palace takeover is dark and militaristic. Hope is contrasted with despair. The warm sunny light right before Iroh and Zuko enter the palace suggest a new beginning. In the cave, the glow of crystals signals possibility of healing but also imprisonment. When Azula takes power, lighting becomes harsh and shadows dominate, signalling betrayal and confusion. Contrast between Azula's blue lightning and Iroh's yellow lightning.
<p>Identity How are identities constructed and represented?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do we learn about the character's personal, cultural, and social identity (race, gender, class, language, etc.)? How do these interact or conflict? Zuko has fully embraces living a normal life in Ba Sing Se running a tea shop. The sun is shining. He looks content, not hiding his scar anymore. He striped of anything that used to be culturally him, like being royal, fire bender, powerful. He himself is now a refugee of war he used to actively participate in. - How are these identities made visible or invisible through audiovisual choices (e.g., costume, voice, framing)?

	<p>Costume shifts from armour to simple tea shop outfits to proper Earth Kingdom clothes. Makes him less threatening. His shaved hair has grown, visually representing the passage of time, change and growth. He looks like a teenager. His calmer tone with Katara contrast his earlier rage filled speech. He smiles more and is less angry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What language contribute to identity (choice of words, formality, accent, self-expression)? <p>Zuko's speech is usually direct and defensive ("I have changed") but softens with Katara ("I'm sorry, that's something we have in common"). Katara's accusations ("It's in your blood") echo generational trauma and stereotypes. This is the first of many times where Zuko apologizes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What does the character represent (values, struggles, ideologies, socially, politically, emotionally)? <p>This episode symbolizes the inner battle between good and evil within Zuko. He is at crossroads with destiny vs. choice. What does he think he has to do and what he wants to do.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who or what influences their self-perception? How does the character view themselves and how do others perceive them? Are there contradictions? How are internal conflicts depicted. <p>His self-perception shifts: he sees himself as unworthy, but Iroh and Katara hint that he has potential for good. While Azula convinces him that he is meant for greatness which he can only achieve through joining her (the "bad" side). The conflicting side are represented by external family figures Azula and Iroh. Both show Zuko what he could be. But Azula's side has deeper connection to Zuko's trauma and hurt, when he sides with her, he could be resolved of all these things and return to normal. While Iroh's side mark new beginning and a lot more work to be good.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the character challenge or reinforce stereotypes? <p>Zuko challenges the "villain prince" stereotype by showing depth, vulnerability, and a desire to change. However, siding with Azula reinforces the stereotype of Fire Nation cruelty and cunningness.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - With whom do viewers identify, and why? <p>Viewers empathize with Zuko's inner struggle because he reflects universal conflicts: family expectation, guilt, longing for acceptance.</p>
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<p>Diversity</p> <p>How are differences portrayed and what interactions do they create?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are relationships across different social groups (e.g., nations, cultures, abilities, ages) portrayed? Are individuals showed beyond group labels? What might be missing? <p>Zuko (Fire Nation) and Katara (Southern Water Tribe) find common ground in shared pain (loss of parents, scars of war). This shows individuals beyond group labels. Even though Katara did meet Zuko with hostility at the start, which shows that people in both nations were conditioned to hate the other. For Katara that is justifiable.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the character show pride in their identity and respect others? <p>Zuko does not show pride in his culture until the end where he does see himself as someone who is from the “great” Fire Nation. But in comparison to earlier he respects others.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do characters navigate between different social, cultural, or community spaces? <p>Zuko learns to live among Earth Kingdom citizens, taking on a humble tea shop owner role. A sharp contrast to his royal upbringings. He is forced to see another side of the world, outside of Fire Nation propaganda. He takes on more of Iroh’s characteristics, he is easier going, even is funny at times, less angry. He lets himself be a teenager.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are differences shown as enriching, problematic, or threatening? <p>Differences are initially threatening (Katara distrust Zuko) but become enriching in crystal cave when they share trauma. However, Azula manipulates differences to divide.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does the visual design signal inclusion, exclusion, or hierarchy? <p>Tea shop = inclusion and community. Crystal cave = shared humanity and possible healing. Throne room with Azula and Dai Li = exclusion, hierarchy, and authoritarianism. The different light motifs also tell the viewer what Zuko might be feeling and which side he feels more inclined to join.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What would change if the story was told from another character’s point of view or different setting (period, culture)?
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	<p>If told from Katara’s perspective, the betrayal in the cave would hit even harder. A reminder that trust between enemies can be fragile.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Were there moments that challenged your thinking or made you uncomfortable? <p>Katara’s words about Zuko’s “blood” challenge the viewer to question essentialist thinking about identity and morality. Also, Zuko’s betrayal takes a toll on the viewers good graces, as they have been rooting for him an entire season only for him to fall into old habits.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do you compare your own background and experiences (ethnicity, gender, sexuality, class, age, religion etc.) with those of the characters? <p>It’s hard to sympathize with someone who doesn’t understand their impact (imperialist).</p>
<p>Justice What power structures are shown and how are they challenged?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What forms of bias or injustices (e.g., discrimination, war, imperialism, inequality) are present? What are the consequences? <p>Azula’s coup shows corruption. The Dai Li are under her control using fear and manipulation. Fire Nation imperialism is depicted as systemic oppression. Katara suffers personal injustice (loss of her mother) due to the Fire Nation aggression. Zuko is oppressed and hunted by his own family’s abuse and military action. Iroh is imprinted despite acting with compassion.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which characters benefit from/ has power? How do they use or lose it? <p>Azula benefits most, gaining Ba Sing Se and manipulating Zuko. Zuko temporarily gains power but loses moral ground. Zuko has the power to choose which most don’t have.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who gets away with what and who suffers? - Whose perspective dominates the story? Whose voices are missing or marginalized? <p>Zuko’s choices are central, though Katara and Iroh’s perspectives complicate the narrative. Missing voices are ordinary Ba Sing Se citizens, Earth Kingdom leadership.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are systems of oppression visually encoded (e.g., language, architecture, uniforms, lighting, space)? Dai Li uniforms, dimly lit prisons, Azula's militaristic posture – all visually show authoritarian rule. - Do characters symbolize broader social conflicts or ideologies? - What real-world social or political issues are mirrored in the show (e.g., racism, imperialism, classism)? Mirrors imperialism, colonials, and family abuse cycles. Also speaks to propaganda, betrayal of trust, corruption of power, destiny vs. choice. - What emotional reactions did these injustices evoke in you? Frustration disappointment, sadness – especially when Zuko betrays Iroh, the only figure who truly loves him unconditionally.
<p>Action What responses to injustice are modelled and what might we do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do characters resist injustice or take action for change? What skills, values, or mindsets (empathy, responsibility, agency) help them? Iroh resists oppression through compassion, urging others to see good in Zuko. Zuko is ready to live as a normal guy but given the first choice to not do that he takes it. Katara resist Fire Nation cruelty but opens to empathy. - What are the risks and consequences of speaking out? Speaking out (Iroh's plea to Zuko) risks losing Zuko to Azula. Katara's vulnerability in the cave risks betrayal. Zuko siding with Azula risks permanent moral corruption. - What language or actions express fairness, protest, or resistance? Zuko's refusal to capture Aang in earlier episodes was resistance, but here he falls back. Iroh's sacrifice at the end is the ultimate protest: non-violent, stalling so others may escape. - Are there examples of collective action or allyship? What strategies are used, and how effective are they? The Gaang and Iroh working together to break Katara and Zuko free is an example of tentative allyship. Their strategies show trust building and collective strength.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What narrative or visual tools suggest change or hope (e.g., inspirational scenes, colour shifts, music)? <p>Light motifs suggest possibility of redemption. cave scenes emphasise intimacy through hopeful music change and betrayal through first leitmotif.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How might your interpretation inspire action or reflection? - What should viewers take away from this story? <p>Viewers may reflect on cycles of trauma and betrayal, but also the possibility of empathy and second chances.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What were the creator intention? How does that affect interpretation? <p>Likely to show the complexity of morality, that change is not linear, that temptation is powerful, and that “destiny can be self-chosen.</p>
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Appendix D Season 3, Episode 12 “The Western Air Temple”

Table 9: Observational Notes with Timestamps for Season 3, Episode 12 “The Western Air Temple”

Timestamp	Notes
2.35 – 4.06	<p>After losing the battle against the Fire Nation and Fire Lord Ozai, the Gaang walks back to the western Air Temple. Unbeknownst to them Zuko has been following them. Zuko has let go of his ponytail is wearing casual Fire Nation clothes. The motif in the background sounds sombre sad, it is not the usual Zuko motif.</p> <p>Flashback: a week after, freshly wounded and banished Zuko shown by the patch by his eye, is at the western air temple is looking for the Avatar. Iroh comments on how beautiful the view is, Zuko is only interested in “seeing the Avatar in chains”. Iroh informs him that the Avatar hasn’t been seen in 100 years. Zuko talks again about regaining his honour.</p> <p>Present Zuko groans at his past behaviour. He hears Appa in the background and does into hiding.</p>
5.33 – 7.01	<p>The Avatar is looking for someone who can teach Zuko how to firebend. Meanwhile Zuko is rehearsing how to approach the Gaang. He is bashful, and apologetic. “I’m pretty good at firebending. Well, you have seen me... you know, when I was attacking you. I guess I should apologize for that. Anyway, I’m good now. I mean I thought I was good before, but now I realise I was bad”. He is cute and so awkward. He wants to teach Aang how to firebend. Zoom out to him talking to a from racoon. He gets angry and demands an answer but is immediately defeated when the frog jumps away. He is frustrated knowing that it’ll be very hard to convince the others. So he thinks about what Uncle Iroh would do. Then thinks about what Azula would do. He embodies both character and the way they talk perfectly. He is framed to be funny, and he is frustrated. He is shown to be reflective knows that his past actions will probably alienate the group.</p>
7.34	<p>When the group sees Zuko the previous Fire Nation light motif can be heard. But when he talks “Hi Zuko here” a small blinking sound can be heard making him look less harmless. The group is ready for attack, also can be heard through their fight light motif. Appa licks Zuko affectionately, comedic. Aang is also taken aback by that, because it must mean that Appa trusts Zuko. The groups are less accepting though, as they’re not surprised, he would be there as he has been following them all over the world. He wants to tell them that he has changed. And that he is good now and that he would teach fire bending. By that the defences of the groups are slightly down, probably out of shock. But they ask him how they could possibly trust him. He says that he did do some good things</p>

	<p>like setting Appa free. He apologizes for all the awful things he did in the past. Aang doesn't talk. So Zuko asks why he doesn't. Aang did say one time that they could be friends and that he knows that he has some good in him. Aang says there is no way he could ever trust him that they would never let him in the group. There is true betrayal on Zuko's face. The group threatens to attack him. So Zuko says that if they won't accept him as a friend they should take him as prisoner, he goes onto his knees and hold his hands up. They won't do that either. Zoom in on Aang's face might indicate that he feels conflicted even change his mind?</p>
10.39 – 10.57	<p>Zuko is talking to himself again, how stupid he was for saying all the things he did. He is mad with himself, but it's framed to be comedic.</p>
13.25 – 14.10	<p>The groups talk about all the good and the bad things Zuko has done over the years, like talking about their mothers with Katara, setting Aang free from Zhao and helping Appa. Toph comments that considering his messed-up family background that he could be way worse. Katara comments that his bare minimum behaviour shouldn't be awarded. Toph says that he was sincere that maybe because of hurt feelings the other can't think clearly. Most importantly Aang needs a firebender teacher and Zuko is their only option. Toph gets angry when Aang is against it "I'm wondering if I'm the only blind one here."</p> <p>While Zuko is sleeping Toph goes to visit him. Scared that he is being attacked Zuko firebends which hurts Toph's feet. The most important body part for her. She crawls away from him. Zuko cries out in frustration "Why am I so bad at being good?"</p> <p>Toph knows it was accident and takes him into protection. But the group still wants to him as a prisoner because he is too dangerous.</p>
16.30	<p>Combustion Man is back to attacking the group. Zuko swings in in to stop him. Indiana Jones type light motif in the background, signalling that the is the hero. By Sokka hitting the third eye of Combustion Man with his boomerang he destroys himself. Bright hopeful light motif follows Zuko.</p>
19.45	<p>Aang thanks Zuko. Zuko explains thoroughly how he has changed. He had to go through all these things to learn the truth and become who he is today. "I thought I had lost my honour and that somehow my father could return it to me. But I know now that no one can give you your honour. It's something you earn for yourself by choosing to do what's right. All I want now is to play my part in ending this war. And I know my destiny is to help you restore balance to the world." Zuko is sincere and apologetic. Aang is softening up. Hopeful light motif. Zuko apologises for hurting Toph. He says the needs to learn to be more careful so that he doesn't</p>

	<p>unintentionally hurts anyone. This also being Aang biggest fear while firebending realises that Zuko is supposed to be his teacher. They bow in respect to each other and Zuko thanks him. That doesn't mean he is accepted into the group nor that the others think of him as a friend. Aang learning firebending and defeating the fire lord is more important. The shot of where Zuko enthusiastically goes up to them, but the group just leaves him standing is pretty devastating. Zuko is happy nonetheless. Sokka shows Zuko his room and is awkward about it, but Zuko is just content smiling. Zuko packs out a picture of Iroh.</p> <p>Flashback: Zuko talks about destiny being him capturing the Avatar. Iroh answers that destiny is a funny thing, you never know how things are going to work out. If he keeps an open mind and open heart Zuko will find his own destiny someday.</p> <p>Present day. Katara says he isn't fooled by transformation. She threatens him. Zuko looks scared. Light motif reflects that.</p>
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Table 10: Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework applied to Season 3, Episode 12 "The Western Air Temple"

<p>Visual Scene Decoder</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is your immediate gut reaction to the scene? <p>This episode feels awkward, tense, frustrating, but also comedic. Zuko's rehearsing and Appa's affection soften his entrance, while the groups stay on high alert. I can see the sincerity and know the journey Zuko has been, but the Gang doesn't that why its untestable and frustrating why they don't want to include him the Group nevertheless be friends with him. It also doesn't help that he Zuko has been messing up. As he put it "Why am I so bad at being good?". A masterclass in representing identity conflict, cross-cultural reconciliation and justice through personal transformation. The episodes used audio shift, comedy, and sincerity to make viewers both laugh and empathize while forcing reflection on how people earn trust, resist oppression and define honour beyond inherited power.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is literally depicted? <p>Zuko approaches the Gaang, awkwardly apologizes and offers to be Aang's firebending teacher. He is rejected multiple times. He redeems himself during Combustion Man's attack and delivers a heartfelt speech about redefining honour.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What mood or atmosphere is communicated?
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	<p>Sombre flashbacks and motifs highlight his guilt and past mistakes, while comedic beats (Zuko talking to a frog, Appa licking him) show his vulnerability. The atmospheres teeters between tension and hope, reflecting his transformation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What were the creator intention? How does that affect interpretation? <p>The creators deigned this episode probably to be dramatize Zuko's turning pint at last. The shift from villain to ally. By combining humour, suspense and emotional sincerity, they allow the audience to empathize with him while still acknowledging his past harm</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do viewers emotionally connect and identify with the characters, compare their own backgrounds and experiences to them, and, through this empathy, what reflections or actions might be inspired in response to the injustices portrayed? <p>Viewers empathize with Zuko's desire for acceptance and fear of rejection, mirroring universal experiences of wanting forgiveness. His awkwardness makes him relatable. Ath the same time his sincerity forces viewers to consider how change and redemption can happen after deem harm.</p>
<p>Identity How are identities constructed and represented?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What do we learn about the character's personal, cultural, and social identity (race, gender, class, language, etc.)? How do these interact or conflict? <p>Zuko's past identity is clashing with. His growing identity as someone seeking justice and balance. He has left his royals status for good to became an ally of the Avatar rejecting everything.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are these identities made visible or invisible through audiovisual choices (e.g., costume, voice, framing)? <p>Zuko is wearing casual Fire Nation clothes instead of royal clothing/armour. He doesn't wear a top knot anymore and lets his hair fall loosely. He is accompanied by the strong light motif anymore but by something more sombre which is also used for the group.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What language contribute to identity (choice of words, formality, accent, self-expression)

	<p>His language shifts from aggressive to awkwardly apologetic (“I guess I should apologize... I thought I was good before, but now I realise I was bad.”) His speech is hesitant, unpolished and humble. Contrasting sharply with his past where he was full of (fake) confidence and authority. This marks his identity as someone learning vulnerability rather than dominance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What does the character represent (values, struggles, ideologies, socially, politically, emotionally)? <p>He is traitor of the Fire Nation. Acceptance of peers. Themes of redemption, honour as self-defined and rejection of imperial ideology.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the character challenge or reinforce stereotypes? <p>Instead of the stereotype of the unredeemable villain, Zuko complicates it by sincerely struggling with his mistakes. He takes accountability. He challenges the idea that masculinity and firebending must be tied to anger and aggression.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does the character view themselves and how do others perceive them? Are there contradictions ? How are internal conflicts depicted? <p>Zuko sees himself as sincere and willing to help, but the group perceives him as dangerous and untrustworthy. This contradiction drives much of the tension.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - With whom do viewers identify, and why? <p>Many viewers identify with his struggle for acceptance after failure and also owing up to that failure. His vulnerability makes him easier to empathize with than the more secure characters.</p>
<p>Diversity How are differences portrayed and what interactions do they create?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are relationships across different social groups (e.g., nations, cultures, abilities, ages) portrayed? Are individuals showed beyond group labels? What might be missing? <p>The Gaang represents multicultural unity (Water Tribe, Earth Kingdom, Air Nomad, blind Earthbender). Zuko’s attempt to join them symbolizes bridging national and cultural divides. His inclusion takes a long while and is debated, showing how trust across groups takes works. The Gaang is shown to be helping Toph when can’t anymore without needing to be asked. Her blindness is something so normal which they work with, full of consideration.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the character show pride in their identity and respect others? Zuko begins to show shame about his Fire Nation identity (“The World hates us, and we deserve it” but reframes it by choosing to teach Aang responsibly. - How do characters navigate between different social, cultural, or community spaces? Zuko shift from Fire Nation royalty to exile to ally, moving between social/cultural communities with difficulty. - Are differences shown as enriching, problematic, or threatening? Initially difference is treated as threatening, (The Gaang rejects him) but by the end, difference becomes potentially enriching (he is the only one who can teach firebending) - How does the visual design signal inclusion, exclusion, or hierarchy? Motifs reinforce his outside status (fire nation theme, sombre music, hostile framing) while the light motif shift to hopeful once he proves himself. The group physically leaves him standing alone, visually reinforcing exclusion, that they can tolerate him but are not friends. - What would change if the story was told from another character’s point of view or different setting (period, culture)? If told from Katara’s POV the narrative would highlight grief and mistrust. From Toph’s POV it would emphasise Zuko’s sincerity and shared outsider status. - Were there moments that challenged your thinking or made you uncomfortable? It was irritating to see how the Group wouldn’t accept him. Here I should have had more understanding for the Gang. Zuko was awful to them. - How do you compare your own background and experiences (ethnicity, gender, sexuality, class, age, religion etc.) with those of the characters?
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	Viewers might compare their own experience of exclusion, prejudice, or mistrust with Zuko's rejection, sparking empathy for "outsiders" in real life.
<p>Justice</p> <p>What power structures are shown and how are they challenged?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What forms of bias or injustices (e.g., discrimination, war, imperialism, inequality) are present? What are the consequences? <p>The group's mistrust, though justifies, also shows the difficulty of forgiveness and reintegration after harm.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which characters benefit from/ has power? How do they use or lose it? <p>Zuko relinquishes his inherited power (royal status) in favour of earned moral authority, the gang still hold the power to reject or accept him.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Whose perspective dominates the story? Whose voices are missing or marginalized? <p>The group's suspicion dominates the episode, while Zuko's voice struggles to be heard, Katara's scepticism highlights the silenced victim's perspective.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are systems of oppression visually encoded (e.g., language, architecture, uniforms, lighting, space)? <p>By dressing plain Zuko symbolically rejects imperial structures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do characters symbolize broader social or political conflicts or ideologies (e.g., racism, imperialism, classism)? <p>Zuko represent the possibility of breaking generational cycles of violence and choosing justice over loyalty to oppressive systems.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What emotional reactions did these injustices evoke in you? <p>Viewers may feel pity, hope, and unease- torn between wanting to forgive him and remembering his past cruelty.</p>
<p>Action</p> <p>What responses to injustice are modelled and what might we do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do characters resist injustice or take action for change? What skills, values, or mindsets (empathy, responsibility, agency) help them? <p>Zuko models taking responsibility, apologizing, actively standing against his father's imperialism. He uses his skills not for domination but to protect others.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the risks and consequences of speaking out? His choice risks total rejection (and even his life) from both sides, his father's wrath and the Gaang's mistrust. - What language or actions express fairness, protest, or resistance? His line "No one can give you honour. It's something you earn for yourself by choosing to do what's right" reframes fairness as self-responsibility and moral courage. - Are there examples of collective action or allyship? What strategies are used, and how effective are they? Toph advocates for him, and Sokka awkwardly offers him a room. These small gestures of allyship foreshadow his eventual integration. - What narrative or visual tools suggest change or hope (e.g., inspirational scenes, colour shifts, music)? Hopeful music, and brighter lighting in the closing scenes suggest optimism and change, even as the group remains distrustful. - How might your interpretation inspire action or reflection? Zuko's arc may inspire reflection on forgiveness, accountability, and the possibility of change, even for those who have caused harm.
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Appendix E Overview of Zuko's character arc in *Avatar: The Last Airbender*

From Season 1, episode 1 to Season 1, episode 12 "The storm"

World and Story Setup

The world of *Avatar: The Last Airbender* is divided into four nations: Water, Earth, Fire, and Air. Each nation is tied to an element that certain people, called "benders", can manipulate. The Avatar, a person reincarnated every generation, can master all four elements and is responsible for maintaining balance in the world. Aang, a young Airbender, discovers that he is the Avatar, but overwhelmed by the responsibility, he flees from home. His disappearance leaves the world vulnerable to the Fire Nation's aggression. In the 100 years after Aang's disappearance, the Fire Nation started an imperialistic war to take over the world. In the present day, by accident, the Avatar is discovered by Katara and Sokka in the Southern Water Tribe. Together with Aang's flying bison, Appa, the three of them embark on a journey to find teachers who can help Aang master the other three elements and restore peace in the world. Their first stop is the Northern Water Tribe, where both Katara and Aang can deepen their knowledge of waterbending.

Introduction of Prince Zuko

Prince Zuko is introduced as the villain. He is the exiled heir of the Fire Nation, driven by the obsession of capturing the Avatar. He is the hot-headed pursuer of the young "hero" and is clearly positioned as the antagonist. His obsession with honour and his temper dominate this characterization. He clashes not only with Team Avatar, but also with the Gaang, which is comprised of Aang and his friends and allies, but also with rival Fire Nation officers, like Commander Zhao, revealing his fragile status within his own country. His desperation to redeem himself in his father's eyes is more important than loyalty to the Nation.

Understanding Zuko

For the first time in episode 12, the audience learns the reason why Zuko is the way he is. His Uncle Iroh tells the story to make soldiers, who were angered by Zuko, develop a deeper understanding of Zuko behind the mask. Zuko was scarred and

banished by his own father, Fire Lord Ozai, after speaking out in a war meeting. His punishment was because he showed compassion for soldiers he didn't want to send to die needlessly, and because he didn't want to fight his father in the Agni Kai duel. The audience sees that he is both victim and aggressor. He is scarred by his father's cruelty, and yet he is repeating cycles of abuse and violence in pursuit of honour. He is a figure driven by shame and trauma, paralleling Aang's own guilt for abandoning his role as the Avatar. Their stories told side by side in this episode highlight how both the hero and the villain are struggling with identity, responsibility, and the weight of past mistakes.

From Season 1, episode 13 to Season 2, episode 7 "Zuko Alone"

The Blue Spirit

In season 1 episode 13, Zuko, disguised as the "Blue Spirit", secretly rescues Aang from Fire Nation captivity. Even though they remain enemies, this shows Zuko's desperation. If he is not the one capturing the Avatar, there is also no way he is restoring his honour. This brief alliance is the first crack in dissolving their rivalry.

Zuko continues to hunt Aang. He even hires a bounty hunter who tracks down the Gaang using Katara's lost necklace. His hunt becomes more dangerous and erratic, reflecting his growing frustration.

Season 1 Finale

In the season 1 finale, during the Fire Nation attack on the Northern Water Tribe, Zuko attempts to capture Aang, but fails. In a crucial moment, Admiral Zhao kills the Moon Spirit, the source of all waterbending. Iroh and Zuko defeat Zhao, showing their moral limits. When Zhao dies, Zuko is left conflicted, as he fought against his own nation but gained nothing.

Life on the Run

At the beginning of season 2, Iroh and Zuko are branded as traitors and are now fugitives, living below their means and hiding from the Fire Nation. Azula, Zuko's younger sister, is introduced. She is a firebending prodigy, who is cold, manipulative, and ruthless, she is the embodiment of the Fire Nation's cruelty. She lures Iroh and Zuko in

with the false promise of forgiveness from the Fire Lord if they return home with her. They refuse, flee the scene, and cut off their topknots, a Fire Nation symbol of loyalty, cutting ties with their past lives. Azula recruits her childhood friends Mai and Ty Lee to aid her in hunting down Zuko and Iroh, forming a deadly trio.

Zuko among Ordinary People

On the run and living in poverty, Zuko and Iroh experience life among ordinary people. They see the effect the war has on normal citizens. Iroh's compassion earns them kindness, while Zuko wrestles with bitterness. In "Avatar Day" Zuko, disguised as the Blue Spirit, steals food from villagers, crossing a line with Iroh. Wanting to find his way in life, Zuko decides to travel alone.

In season 2 episode 7, Zuko wanders alone through the Earth Kingdom villages. The episode parallels a Western and focuses entirely on him. Through flashbacks, we see his childhood: the kindness of his mother and how she disappeared, Azula's cruelty, and Ozai's rejection. In the present, he forms a bond with a kind family and defends a small village from corrupt soldiers, but when he reveals his Fire Nation identity, he earns their fear and rejection. This is a very vulnerable portrait of Zuko, as he is isolated, dejected, and torn between being the victim of his family's abuse and the oppressor others see him as.

From Season 2, episode 8 to Season 2, episode 20 "The Crossroads of Destiny"

Encounters with the Gaang

The Gaang has a new addition, a blind earthbender called Toph. While trying to defeat Azula, Mai and Ty Lee, they get unexpected help from Zuko and Iroh. Iroh gets hurt in the process, which causes Zuko to lash out at the Gaang.

Zuko and Iroh are still fugitives but are secretly protected from Fire Nation bounty hunters by the Order of the White Lotus, a secret society Iroh belongs to. Zuko grows more independent, learning how to redirect lightning from Iroh to be more capable against Azula. Redirecting lightning is a technique symbolizing balance and control, trying to unlearn his usual aggression.

Life in Ba Sing Se

Zuko and Iroh finally find a tiny bit of peace in the Earth Kingdom city Ba Sing Se, opening a tea shop. For the first time in their lives, they live a normal life, free from war and pursuit. Zuko even goes on a date with a kind girl, showing glimpses of the gentler, compassionate person, he could become. While Aang is desperately searching for his lost bison, Zuko secretly discovers Appa. Instead of turning Appa over to Azula or the Fire Nation or using him as a decoy to capture Aang, he releases him. This marks a pivotal point in Zuko's growth.

Crossroads of Destiny

Zuko becomes physically ill, "a spiritual fever" reflecting his inner conflict. He has taken steps forward, rejecting the Fire Nation's cruelty, but his old identity still holds onto him. Iroh sees this as a sign that Zuko is at crossroads in his destiny.

In episode 20 "The Crossroads of Destiny," Zuko and Iroh are tricked into Azula's schemes. Zuko's struggle peaks when Azula offers him the one thing he desperately craves: getting his honour back and his father's acceptance. In a devastating turn, Zuko chooses Azula's side, betraying Iroh and the Gaang, thus helping her overthrow Ba Sing Se. Season two ends with Zuko regaining his status in the Fire Nation, but at the cost of the integrity and moral progress he had begun.

From Season 3, episode 1 to Season 3, episode 12 "The Western Air Temple" and Season 3, episode 21

Return to the Fire Nation

Zuko returns to the Fire Nation as a hero who supposedly killed the Avatar. He now has everything he ever thought he wanted: honour restored, love from Mai, and acceptance from his nation. Yet beneath the surface, he feels hollow. He visits Iroh in prison, but his uncle refuses to speak to him, leaving him even more conflicted. In secret, Zuko hires an assassin, Combustion Man, to kill Aang, to prove that he did it, and show that he still cannot let go of his father's expectations. Zuko learns more about his lineage. His maternal grandfather was Avatar Roku (the Avatar before Aang), and his paternal Grandfather was Fire Lord Sozin. Both used to be best friends until Sozin ignored Roku's request to keep the Nations separate and not invade them by starting

a war. Zuko is now the living embodiment of both sides, imperialist and protector, forcing him to confront the duality of his destiny.

Turning Point

During “The Day of the Black Sun” when the Gaang invades the Fire Nation, Zuko makes his pivotal choice. He confronts his father directly and declares that he didn’t kill the Avatar and that honour isn’t about obedience. His deepest desire was never power but his father’s love, which he finally sees he will never have. Growing up, he thought that the Fire Nation was the greatest civilization in the world and that they were just spreading their greatness all over the world, but the rest of the world was terrified of them. They created an end of an era which can only be replaced by peace and kindness. When Ozai strikes him with lightning, Zuko redirects it, symbolizing this mastery over both fire and his identity. He chooses to leave everything behind and join the Avatar.

Joining the Gaang

In episode 12, “The Western Air Temple” shows Zuko trying to join the Gaang. At first, the Gaang rejects him, remembering his betrayals. But through humility and persistence, Zuko wins their trust. This episode represents identity conflict, cross-cultural reconciliation, and justice through personal transformation. Later in episode 13, with Aang, Zuko seeks the true meaning of firebending, discovering it is rooted not in anger but in life and creation. This turning point shows Zuko rebuilding himself piece by piece. Zuko travels with the Gaang, teaching Aang firebending while also reconciling with Katara and Sokka. In “The Southern Raiders” he helps Katara confront her mother’s killer, showing his commitment to justice and healing.

Final Arc

When the final battle is ahead, Zuko is fully integrated into the team, standing alongside Aang as an ally, rather than an enemy. During Sozin’s Comet, Zuko duels Azula for the Fire Nation throne. She crumbles under her own paranoia, while Zuko, with Katara’s help, defeats her. This was a moment of symbolic closure. Meanwhile, Aang spares Ozai’s life but strips him of his bending powers, ending the cycle of war without perpetuating violence. Zuko becomes Fire Lord, vowing to rebuild the world with peace and balance.

Appendix F Anti-Bias Media Analysis Framework Diagram

Figure 2: Anti-Bias Media Analysis Diagram (Full-Page Version of Figure 6.1). Design elements sourced from ©Sabina Alcaraz via Canva.com.

ANTI-BIAS MEDIA ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK

Learning For Justice (2022), Eder (2010), McLaughlin & DeVoogd (2004), Freitag-Hild (2022), Doeiker (2015), Doeiring (2013)

Based on a template by Sabina Alcaraz (Canva) modified by Abitha Ranganathan

Figure 4: Anti-Bias Media Analysis Diagram Blank Template. Design elements sourced from ©Sabina Alcaraz via Canva.com.

